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Deliverable 21.1

EU-HARMONISED AND COMPARATIVE MEASUREMENT OF OCCUPATIONS AND SKILLS

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European policy-oriented research can and must deliver useful contributions to tackle the Europe 2020 challenges of Inclusive Growth. Key tools in this social sciences research are all types of data earning statistics, administrative social data, labour market data, surveys on quality of life or working conditions, policy indicators. The project aims to integrate and optimise these existing European data infrastructures and accompanying expertise.

Abstract

This report is a deliverable of Work Package 21 ‘Innovative tools and protocols for working conditions & vulnerability research.’ Section 2 provides a review of the measurement of occupations in surveys in Europe. It specifies how occupations are measured in web surveys, and outlines the methodology currently used to test the comparability of the job content and skill requirements in occupational titles. The results of the validation efforts are presented, including the design of a project to measure occupations on a global scale. Occupation is a key variable in socio-economic research, used in a wide variety of studies. Where such studies use quantitative approaches, they usually rely on survey data. In this paper an inventory of 33 surveys is analysed with respect to the phrasing of the question. The vast majority uses an open text format for the occupation question, but the phrasing of the question is different across almost all surveys. In an additional question, half of the surveys ask for a job description, and again the phrasing varies largely across the surveys. Coding of the open format question is usually (semi-) automatic, survey agencies applying dictionary approaches for automatic occupational coding. In web surveys closed survey questions can be asked using text string matching and search trees for navigating. Recently, machine learning algorithms appear to be a promising development, requiring a substantial amount of manually coded occupations to be used as training data for the automatic classification. A huge training set is required for an auto-coder to apply machine learning algorithms. This Section details a design to develop such a training set in a multi-country approach.

Occupation is a key variable in socio-economic research, used in a wide variety of studies, but the measurement of occupations is a major challenge. In case of open-ended survey questions, web surveys pose extra challenges, as respondents are more likely to key in odd text compared to other survey modes, particularly those with an interviewer. Web surveys however offer new opportunities for closed survey questions with self-identification of occupations, particularly when using semantic matching and a database with large numbers of coded occupational titles. Section 3 details the design requirements for such a database to facilitate surveys in multiple countries. First, this Section describes how the WISCO Database of Occupations has developed since its first use in 2000, when the database was applied in the WageIndicator web survey on work and wages. By the end of 2015 the web survey and the database had expanded to 85 countries. In these fifteen years, the number of occupations in the database had increased from 55 to 1,896 and the languages covered from 1 to 43. The section then presents an overview of the ISCO occupational classification with four hierarchical levels and their coding. It also reviews how occupations can be measured in web surveys in open-ended or closed survey questions. For the closed question three approaches are detailed, notably scrolling, search trees and semantic matching. Given that any national labour market easily cover 10,000 or more occupational titles, the semantic matching is considered the best approach provided that the look-up tables include 5,000 or more occupational titles for each country. Finally, the Section details the design principles in the database used for semantic matching. It discusses the size of the source list in relation to the ISCO coding. It details the issue of male and female titles and the use of start or end years for occupations. It specifies how the database copes with highly aggregated occupational titles such as clerk or manager, with abbreviations and organisation specific job titles, with synonyms, with skill levels within and across occupations, with occupations in the corporate hierarchy, with composite jobs, with handicraft workers, and with subsistence farmers and hunters. Next, it details how to cope with respondents indicating that their job title is not in the database. The Section ends with a future outlook for a program to test the validity and reliability of occupational measurement.

Section 4 addresses the question whether occupations refer to the same work activities, as assumed in occupational classifications such as ISCO-08? Up to now, no large-scale empirical testing of this

assumption has been conducted, whereas occupations are a core variable in socio-economic research. Using the task descriptions provided for all ISCO-08 4-digit occupations, the frequency of task implementation was tested using respondents in the multi-country, multilingual WageIndicator web survey on work and wages in 13 countries. The web survey targets individuals in the labour force. Depending on their self-selected occupation, the relevant task list was shown and respondents were asked to tick on a 5-point scale how often they performed each task. For 427 occupations (ISCO-08 4-digits) in total 3,237 occupation-specific tasks were available. Between November 2013 and August 2015 33,678 respondents had completed the tasks questions for their respective occupations. The results show that task measurement is feasible because it can generate sufficient observations to allow for analysis for a range of detailed, 4-digit occupations. Moreover, given that the WageIndicator web survey also holds data on wages, the median and average hourly wages (in euro) could be computed for each task separately, showing that the average wages of tasks performed on a daily or weekly basis ranged between 5 and 34 euro. The data collection challenges future empirical testing of hypotheses concerning the variation in task frequencies and their related wage premiums within and across countries, across occupations' skill levels, across firm sizes, across regions and alike.

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1. Introduction

1.1 InGRID Work Package 21

InGRID Work Package 21 aimed to develop innovative tools and protocols for working conditions & vulnerability research. Annex I - ‘Description of Work’ of the Project: ‘Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion’ (InGRID) Grant agreement no: 312691 details the specific objectives of WP21:

- integrate existing repositories on European and national working conditions and occupational safety and health (WC&OSH) data using a web-based platform;
- integrate and further develop tools and competences in the collection of cross-country comparative WC&OSH data;
- design and implement a web-portal that provides the research community and stakeholders with classification and analytical tools for WC&OSH analysis;
- develop new methods and tools to generate comparative WC&OSH data of relevance for the EU new skills new jobs strategy;
- contribute in an innovative way to the development of an integrated research infrastructure on WC&OSH analysis with a focus on vulnerable groups.

Work Package 21 consisted of four tasks. This paper concerns the first one, task 21.1 ‘New skills new jobs: tools for harmonising the measurement of occupations’, by Kea Tijdens, research coordinator at the University of Amsterdam/Amsterdam Institute for Advanced Labour Studies (AIAS). Task 21.1 included four milestones, as presented in Table 1.1. The table also presents the titles and links of the related papers.

Table 1.1 Overview of tasks, milestones and delivered papers in task 21.1

Task #	Task label and paper	MS #	Milestone label and link to paper	Delivery date
Task 21.1.1	Review the existing knowledge on tools used to measure occupations in EU Member States in various survey modes	MS93	Review of tools measuring occupations in surveys	
Paper	Tijdens K. (2014). Reviewing the measurement and comparison of occupations across Europe.		https://inclusivegrowth.be/downloads/output/m21-2-working-paper-measurement-kea-tijdens.pdf	Aug-14
Task 21.1.2	Develop methods to facilitate the testing of the comparability of the job content of occupational titles as well as the skill requirements for these occupations across EU Member States	MS94	Methods to facilitate EU- wide comparability of occupations	
Paper	Tijdens K. & de Visintin S. (2016). What do workers do? Measuring the intensity and market value of tasks in jobs		https://inclusivegrowth.be/downloads/output/m21-3.pdf	Jan-15
Task 21.1.3	Develop methods to facilitate the EU-wide measurement of occupations in web surveys using an Application programming interface (API)	MS95	Methods to facilitate EU- wide measurement of occupations	
Paper	Tijdens K. (2015). The design of a tool for the measurement of occupations in web surveys using a global index of occupations		https://inclusivegrowth.be/downloads/output/m21-4-coding-tool-eind.pdf	Dec-15
Task 21.1.4	Validate these research efforts on standardisation and harmonisation with an expert group of data collectors and data users	MS96	Expert group validation of results ‘occupations’	
	Workshop 10-12 February 2014 Workshop 7-8 November 2016		https://inclusivegrowth.be/events/call6-ExpertWorkshop https://inclusivegrowth.be/events/call41/expert-workshop-call41	Feb-14 Nov-16

1.2 Outline of this report

This report is based on the three papers and the two workshops listed in Table 11. Section 2 addresses deliverable for Task 21.1.1, the review the existing knowledge. Section 3 refers to Task 21.1.3, the design of a tool for the measurement of occupations. Section 4 does so to Task 21.1.2, the testing of the comparability of the job content. Note that the sequence for the latter two sections is reversed compared to the initial task list in Table 1.1, because content-wise the sequence in this report is more logical. Section 5 details the two workshops.

The three initial papers included several appendixes, some of which are very long. This report does not include these appendixes, but instead has a link to the relevant papers. Two of the three papers have also been published as an UVA-AIAS working paper and are downloadable from the AIAS website (Tijdens, 2014; Tijdens & Visintin, 2016).

1.3 Acknowledgements

This paper was written for the InGRID - Inclusive Growth Infrastructure Diffusion - project, which has received funding from the 7th Framework Program of the European Union [Contract no. 312691, 2013/02 - 2017/02]. InGRID is co-ordinated by HIVA-KU Leuven-KU Leuven, Belgium.¹

For Section 4 the authors thank Brian Fabo, who in 2013 and 2014 was the data and survey manager of the WageIndicator web survey. In September 2013 and in May 2014 he could visit AIAS/University of Amsterdam, discuss the design of the task measurement in the WageIndicator web survey and

¹ See <https://inclusivegrowth.be/news>

conduct a first analysis thanks to two InGRID visiting grants. He could solve the technical challenges related to the task measurement in the survey. The authors also acknowledge the WageIndicator Foundation, providing the data used Section 4. The Foundation bears no responsibility for the analyses or interpretation of the data reported here. The second author (Stefano Visintin) acknowledges the support from the EDUWORKS Marie-Curie ITN network, funded by the 7th Framework Program of the European Union [Contract no. 608311]. The authors thank Paulien Osse (WageIndicator Foundation, Amsterdam), Tomas Kabina (CELSI Bratislava), Emil Mihaylov (VU Amsterdam), and Duco Dokter and Huub Bouma (Wyldebeast & Wunderliebe, Groningen) for their contributions in various stages of the project.

For Sections 2, 3, and 4 the acknowledgements are extended to the WageIndicator Foundation for adapting the database of occupations in its web survey. The Foundation is a non-profit organisation, established 17-9-2003 and dedicated to labour market transparency by providing accurate wage and wage related information, using Internet. Its founders are the University of Amsterdam/AIAS, the Dutch Confederation of Trade Unions (FNV), and career website Monster.

The research undertaken in Task 21.1 builds on previous EU-funded projects, notably WOLIWEB (EU-FP6, no 506590, 2004-2006), EurOccupations (EU-FP6-028987, 2006/05-2009/04), and EDUWORKS (Marie Curie Initial Training Network, no. 608311, 2013/09-2017/08). The work developed under this InGRID grant will be continued in the SERISS project (EU-Horizon 2020, no 654221, 2015/07-2019/06), aiming to develop a cross-country harmonised, multi-lingual, web-based coding module for the measurement of occupation in socio-economic surveys, to be used in 99 countries, covering 47 languages.²

² See <http://seriss.eu/about-seriss/work-packages/wp8-a-coding-module-for-socio-economic-survey-questions/>, accessed 20 January 2017

2. Reviewing the measurement and comparison of occupations across Europe

Author: Kea Tjzens, University of Amsterdam, Netherlands

2.1 Introduction

This section addresses Task 21.1.1 ‘Review the existing knowledge on tools used to measure occupations in EU Member States in various survey modes’ (see Table 1.1). The outline of this paper is as follows. Section 2.2 provides a review of the measurement of occupations in surveys in Europe. Section 2.3 specifies how exactly occupations are measured in web surveys. Section 2.4 details the results of the validation efforts, including the design of a project to measure occupations on a global scale.

2.2 Review of the measurement of occupations in surveys in Europe

2.2.1 Introduction

Occupation is a key variable in socio-economic research, used in a wide variety of studies, among others for school-to-work transitions, manpower forecasting, the gender pay gap, skill obsolescence, occupational health and safety, processes of professionalisation, and social stratification (see for the latter Lambert & Bihagen, 2014). Where such studies use quantitative approaches, they usually rely on survey data. This section reviews how occupations are measured in surveys, more specifically how survey questions and answers are phrased in various survey modes, and which coding practices and coding classifications are used. The section is based on an inventory of survey questions and answers in 33 surveys and on a review of coding practices and classifications.

2.2.2 Survey questions and answers for the measurement of occupations

In many surveys the occupation variable is collected via questions such as ‘What is your occupation?’, ‘What kind of work do you do?’ or similar (Hoffmann *et al.*, 1995). Yet, to the best of my knowledge, no overview of survey questions for the measurement of occupations is available. Therefore an own inventory of the occupation question in surveys was drafted. Questionnaires were selected that were firstly free available at the Internet and secondly in a language understood by the author (English, German, French, Dutch). The inventory includes 33 surveys, held in Europe and the United States (see Table 2.1 and Annex 2 in Tjzens, 2014c). The 33 surveys fall apart in international surveys such as the European Social Survey (ESS) or the European Working Conditions Survey (EWCS), national Labour Force Surveys held by National Statistical Offices, and other national surveys such as the German Socio-Economic Panel (SOEP). For the international surveys and the Labour Force Surveys, the English language versions were taken, resulting in 28 English surveys. In total 23 of the 33 surveys were designed for face-to-face interviews, some of them computer-assisted. The remainders aimed at postal/paper surveys or web surveys, or the survey mode was unknown. 21 surveys were held in the period 2007-2014, the remainders were held in the early 2000’s and two were held in the

late 1990's. Table 2.1 shows the survey questions about job title or occupation asked in these 33 surveys.

Table 2.1 Survey questions about job title or occupation (duplicates not included)

Survey_ID	Survey questions - OPEN FORMAT
ISSP_2008	And in your current job, what is your main occupation? If you are not working now, please tell us about your last job.
WVS_2005/06	In which profession/occupation are you doing most of your work?
WVS_1999-2002	In which profession/occupation do you or did you work? If more than one job, the main job? What is/was your job there?
CPS_US_2013	Kind of Work (Occupation)
VIONA_BE_2000	Kunt u de naam en een bondige omschrijving geven van uw huidige functie?
WVS_2010/12	NO Q ABOUT OCCUPATION, ONLY ABOUT EMPLOYMENT STATUS
EWCS_1995	Now, we would like to obtain some information about your work, more specifically your main paid job. What is your main paid job? Please give me your job title?
EFT_BE_2013	Quelle est votre profession ou votre fonction dans votre activité principale ?
NEA_NL_2013	Uw beroep: Wat is uw beroep of functie?
SOEP_DE_2013	Welche berufliche Tätigkeit haben Sie damals, in Ihrer ersten Stelle, ausgeübt?
EBB_NL_2014	Welk beroep of welke functie oefent (\$A: u \$B: hij \$C: zij) uit?
WERS_UK_2011	What is the full title of your main job?
SCPR_UK_1997	What is the name or title of your job?
EWCS_2010_2005	What is the title of your main paid job? By main paid job, we mean the one where you spend most hours.
AKU_DK_2011	What is your occupation more precisely (your title)?
HEGESCO_2008	What is your current occupation or job title?
PIAAC_2010	What is your job title?
EWCS_2000	What is your main paid job? Please give me your job title in full.
ECHP_2001	What is your present occupation?
ESS_2012/13_2002	What is/was the name or title of your main job?
ISSP_2010	What kind of work (do you/did you) normally do? That is, what (is/was) your job called?
ACS_US_2014	What kind of work was this person doing?
BHPS_UK_2013	What was your (main) job last week? Please tell me the exact job title and describe fully the sort of work you do.
Survey_ID	Survey questions - CLOSED FORMAT
WORLD HEALTH SURVEY_2002	During the last 12 months, what has been your main occupation?
SHARE_2013_2010	Please look at card {SHOWCARD_ID}. What best describes this job?
EUROCADRES_2005	Profession ou position dans l'entreprise ou l'administration
EQLS_2011/12_2007_2003	What is your current occupation?
EPICURUS_2004	Which description fits best your main job?

Source Inventory of survey questions about occupations (see Appendix 2 in Tijdens, 2014c)

Our review leads to the following conclusions:

- 25 of the 33 surveys use an open text format for the occupation question;
- the phrasing of the open format question is different across almost all 25 surveys;
- the words 'job title' and 'occupation' are used both, in some instances even within one question; from the view point of interview time efficiency, PIAAC's question 'What is your job title?' seems to be the most optimal;
- almost all face-to-face surveys with an open text question include interviewer instructions, such as 'Avoid vague occupational titles such as manager, clerk, or farmer' or 'Write in full details';
- almost all postal/paper or web surveys with an open text question include an instruction for the respondent, such as 'Describe fully, using two words or more (do not use initials or abbreviations)' or 'e.g. primary school teacher, state registered nurse, car mechanic, benefits assistant. If you are a civil servant or local government officer, please give your job title, not your grade or pay band';
- 6 of the 8 surveys with a closed format question provide a show card with the categories of the first level of the International Standard Classification of Occupations ISCO (10 entries), which is in some surveys extended with example occupations within each category; the remaining 2 surveys provide a show card with a mixture of employment status, occupational titles, skill level, and supervisory position.

In the open response format questions, respondents report their job titles as they like, eliciting response at various levels of aggregation. In face-to-face or telephone interviews, the interviewer can control this response by asking details if needed. In self-administered surveys the response cannot be controlled. According to Ganzeboom (2010), the answers are most often detailed job titles, but responses may also be crude, highly aggregated or unidentifiable. Respondents tend to report a detailed job title, as they know it from their employment contract, job classification scheme, collective bargaining agreement, job advertisement, or just from a common understanding in the workplace. In some cases this leads to highly disaggregated occupational titles such as Lithographic stone grinder or to very firm-specific job titles such as Appls Prog I, which are difficult to code. In contrast, some respondents tend to report highly aggregated categories, such as clerk or Teacher, or they may be not specific at all, e.g. employee of department X, senior supervisor, or Dogsboddy.

Survey holders usually have manuals to guide interviewers for this survey question. The manual for the US Current Population Survey for example details how interviewers should deal with inadequate descriptions, because these result in difficult to code occupations (US Census Bureau, 2013). Interviewers are instructed that one word responses to the question on occupation (for example, clerk, engineer, manager, nurse, teacher) are usually far too general to be coded accurately. Whenever very brief responses are given to this question, interviewers should probe to obtain a more specific response. Many of the 33 reviewed surveys therefore ask in an additional question for a job description (see Table 2.2). The conclusions are as follows:

- in the 25 open format surveys, 14 ask for a job description; again the phrasing varies largely across the surveys;
- the face-to-face, postal/paper surveys or web surveys use the job description question alike;
- in one survey the open format occupation question is not followed by a job description question, but by a question asking respondents to identify their occupation in a list of 45 occupational titles, clustered in 11 categories.

Table 2.2 Survey questions about job descriptions (duplicates not included)

SURVEY_ID	Survey questions - OPEN FORMAT
EWCS_2010_2005	Q3 What do you mainly do in your job?
ESS_2012/13_2002	F34 In your main job, what kind of work do/did you do most of the time?
ISSP_2010	MAINSLF B. IF NOT ALREADY ANSWERED, ASK: What (do/did) you actually do in that job? Tell me what (are/were) some of your main duties?
ISSP_2008	Q19a. [[STANDARD BACKGROUND: WRKTYPE: ABCD]] In your current job, for whom do you work? If you are not working now, please tell us about your most recent job.
HEGESCO_2008	F2 Please describe your current main tasks or activities
PIAAC_2010	D_Q01b (OECD) (A) What are your most important responsibilities? Please give a full description.
ECHP_2001	Please describe the principal activity you perform
AKU_DK_2011	B2STILA 9. Continued occupational description (description of specific tasks)
EFT_BE_2013	9d. Décrivez en termes précis votre profession ou fonction.
VIONA_BE_2000	Bondige omschrijving:
SCPR_UK_1997	B3b What kind of work do you do most of the time? What materials/equipment do you use? Text : Maximum 120 characters
WERS_UK_2011	E9 Describe what you do in your main job. Please describe as fully as possible.
BHPS_UK_2013	DESCRIBE FULLY WORK DONE:

Source Inventory of survey questions about occupations (see Appendix 2 in Tijdens, 2014c)

In the closed response format questions, a tick list offers respondents a choice of occupational titles or occupational categories. This self-identification method can be used in all survey modes, but the size of the choice-set varies widely across the modes. Telephone surveys allow for asking at most five highly aggregated occupational categories, otherwise respondents will not memorise. Paper-based or face-to-face surveys allow for a choice of at most 50 categories when using show-cards, showing mostly a mixture of aggregated and disaggregated occupations. A limited choice-set may result in lower data quality, because it is difficult to assure consistency in how respondents fit their own job titles into the highly aggregated categories, thereby introducing aggregation bias (De Vries & Ganzeboom, 2008). Web surveys allow for very large choice-sets, thereby solving the problem of aggregation bias.

2.2.3 Occupational classifications

Before turning to the occupational coding practices, this section briefly details a few occupational classifications. Given the unlimited number of job titles, the responses need to be coded into a limited set of aggregated occupational titles, using occupational classification systems. For this purpose, the statistical agencies of 150 countries associated in the International Labour Organisation (ILO), a United Nations affiliate, have adopted the International Standard Classification of Occupations (ISCO) to harmonise the measurement of occupations, dating back to 1958.³ Revisions were made in 1968, and 1988. Recently the fourth version - ISCO-08 - has been released (Hunter, 2009). The hierarchical ISCO-08 classification distinguishes nine major groups at the highest level of aggregation, stepwise breaking these groups down into 433 occupational units at the classification's lowest 4-digit level. In this paper, we refer to occupations in greater detail, notably at 5-digit level, based on the ISCO-08 classification.

ISCO-08, as was the case for its predecessors, defines a job as a set of work tasks and duties performed by one person. Jobs with the same set of main tasks and duties are aggregated into the 4-digit

³ See <http://www.ilo.org/public/english/bureau/stat/isco/ISCO-08/>, accessed 25 July 2014.

occupation units. On the basis of similarity in the tasks and duties performed, the units are grouped into 3- and 2-digit groups, which in turn on the basis of the skill level are grouped into 1-digit groups (Hunter, 2014).

According to Tomaskovic-Devey (1995), the concept of occupation is especially relevant in comparative research, since studying only jobs limits generalisations to the work organisation context and hampers national or international comparisons. Note that the number of job titles may easily run into tens of thousands, and these jobs may have hundreds of thousands of tasks. The concept of occupation is also relevant for vocational training, targeting at occupations rather than jobs. Hence, occupations are job titles, which are aggregated beyond the organisational context. Table 2.3 depicts the number of units included in each level of the ISCO-08 hierarchical classification.

Table 2.3 Details, logic and number of occupations for ISCO-08

Detail	Logic	Numbers of occupations (est)
ISCO-08 1-digit	Skill level	10
ISCO-08 2-digit	Similarity of task and duties	42
ISCO-08 3-digit	Similarity of task and duties	131
ISCO-08 4-digit	Occupational unit (similarity)	433
Occupational title (5-digit)	Beyond workplace (coding indexes)	1,000+
Job title	Workplace (coding indexes)	10,000+
Work task	Clustered into jobs	100,000+

Source ILO (2012).

In the 1990's, the ILO has undertaken efforts to implement ISCO-88 widely (Hoffmann et al, 1995). At that time, quite number of countries used their own National Occupational Classifications (NOC). These classifications tend to differ cross-nationally with respect to the level of detail, to specific occupational titles included in the classifications, and to their logic (Ganzeboom & Treiman, 1996; Pignatti Morano, 2014). Attempts to harmonise NOC's were, among others, hampered by the fact that ISCO does not allow skill levels of occupations to vary across different national contexts (Elias, 1997). Yet, countries who held their first Labour Force Survey or Census in the late 1980's or in the 1990's mostly adopted ISCO or related versions as their occupational classification. In the early 2000s, ISCO had become the standard classification in many countries (Greenwood, 2004). It has also become the standard to classify occupations in many national and international surveys such as ESS, EVS, ISSP, PIAAC and PISA.⁴ The Commission of the European Communities (2009) has adopted ISCO-08 as its occupational classification, and the European statistical agency Eurostat has put effort in supporting European countries in developing coding indexes for their occupation data collected in Labour Force Surveys and similar surveys.

UNSTATS provides an overview of the occupational classifications used in 149 countries in 2012 (see Appendix 3 in Tjijdens, 2014c).⁵ The overview shows that 78 countries do not apply an occupational classification or do not report using one (53%). The remaining 71 countries apply an occupational classification. 49 of these 71 countries apply the ISCO-08 classification, and another 12 countries still apply ISCO-88. Of these 49+12 countries 14 use extended versions of ISCO, hence providing 5-digit codes. Finally, 10 countries employ their own classification, notably Canada, Germany, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Japan, Russian Federation, Switzerland, United Kingdom and the United States of America. The Netherlands used to have its own classification, but changed to ISCO-08 for its 2012 Labour Force Survey (Westerman & Offermans, 2014). This overview supports the assumption

4 See <http://www.hamyganzeboom.nl/ISCO-08/index.htm>, accessed 28 July 2014.

5 See <http://unstats.un.org/unsd/cr/ctryreg/default.asp?Lq=1> accessed 22 April 2014.

that increasingly ILO's ISCO classification is adopted for labour force and other surveys. Most likely, more countries will adopt ISCO-08 in the years to come.

2.2.4 Coding practices

Only a few of the 33 reviewed surveys ask the interviewer to code the occupation during the interview, using a show card with the 2-digit occupational units (field-coding), but most surveys rely on office-coding. Field- and office-coding is usually done by the field institute. Field-coding is advantageous over office-coding because it allows the interviewer to ask additional information if needed, but in case 4-digit coding is required it needs advanced software on the interviewer's laptop. Office-coding is recoding at a later point in time and is disadvantageous in budget terms and timelines.

Coding occupations into a classification requires a coding index, providing codes for frequently mentioned occupational titles. Many national statistical offices (NSO) have developed such an index and provide coding instructions. For example the Index-SSYK of Statistics Sweden (2012) has 8,670 entries. The Austrian Ö-ISCO-08_Index counts 13,314 entries. The Italian Statistical Office has 5,732 entries in its index (ISTAT, 2013). Statistics Netherlands has 1,396 entries in its publicly available CBS codelijsten-ISCO-08. Its index for occupational coding has approximately 5,000 entries and is based on historical data, thus optimised for answers with the highest frequency (Westerman & Offermans, 2014). The German Institute for Employment Research IAB maintains the German KldB occupational classification, which was updated in 2010 and now has a linking to ISCO-08. Approximately 24,000 job titles are assigned to the KldB 2010 (Paulus & Matthes, 2013). The Office for National Statistics (2010) ONS in the United Kingdom has its own classification SOC2010, which has 28,053 entries in its index. To keep up-to-date with new job titles, SOC2010 users are invited to forward information, which will help in the compilation of the job title index and feed into the work for the next update.

Until recently a coding index was used for manual search, requiring alphabetic sorting of the main words in the occupational titles, as for example can be seen in the ONS coding index. A well-known coding software program is CASCOT and its update CASCOT2000.⁶ CASCOT is among others used by ONS and survey agencies in the United Kingdom. Statistics Netherlands, also using CASCOT, has applied a four step occupational coding process, whereby the first step coding is based on job titles only. If insufficient the job description is included for coding in a second step. If still insufficient the third step coding is based on industry and - for managers - on the closed questions about managerial tasks. Here codes are assigned according to beforehand specified rules. If still indecisive, in a fourth step manual coding is applied, whereby other auxiliary variables might be used (Westerman & Offermans, 2014). Other survey agencies have developed their own software. For coding Eurofound's EWCS for example its survey agency Gallup developed a special software-application to assist the ISCO/NACE coding activity (Gallup Europe, 2010). This software allows for multiple and later modifiable selection of items to be coded in one go, for two levels of coding choosing the appropriate 2-digit category first and choosing the 4-digit category from a filtered list based on 2-digit code, for the possibility of adding a comment to each encoded item, and for the possibility to review and recode already encoded items.

In addition to a coding index and coding software, many survey holders use coding instructions for manual coding. Next to the publication of ISCO-08, ILO has also published such an instruction, called 'ISCO-08 group definitions - Final draft'.⁷ This manual includes instructions which occupations should or should not be classified in which code. In addition, it includes for each 4-digit occupation a job description and a task list.

6 See <http://www2.warwick.ac.uk/fac/soc/ier/software/cascot/> accessed 25 July 2014.

7 See <http://www.ilo.org/public/english/bureau/stat/isco/ISCO-08/> accessed 25 July 2014.

Multi-country datasets are typically surveyed by national survey agencies with the data merged afterwards.⁸ In these cases the survey operations, the question formulations or the coding procedures are mostly not fully harmonised, affecting the comparability of the resulting statistics. The coding instructions are the only source to ensure that the same job titles are coded similarly across countries. The central organisation hardly can exhibit controls over the coding process, particularly not in case of language discrepancies. In the multi-country EWCS coding quality was ensured because for each country the first 50-100 items (test items) of preliminary data were translated into English, and these items were coded independently by all members of the local coding teams in the original language and by one Gallup Europe coder in the English translation (Gallup Europe, 2010). Gallup reports the following: ‘These test codes were compared with one another, and besides calculating percentage of agreement, in the case of ISCO coding detailed comments about the rationale behind Gallup Europe’s coding were provided to facilitate general agreement on coding principles. In the case of NACE coding detailed comments were deemed unnecessary due to generally much higher agreement levels than in the case of ISCO. Test-coding comparisons have been documented in the form of Excel files (one for ISCO and one for NACE for each country). These files contain the measures for the percentage of agreement up to 2-3-4-digits, as well as those items that were coded in the test, and any of the variables that were relevant for coding these ‘test-items’. The differences between codes were discussed (in the form of exchanged comments recorded in the coding comparison Excel files) by local and Gallup Europe’s coders until agreement was reached on final codes of test items and on coding principles. Verbatim responses in the local language and their codes are included in the final dataset in order to offer the possibility for future clarifications/checks. All verbatim replies were submitted with full English translations from Albania, Kosovo and Montenegro to facilitate central quality control.’ (Gallup Europe, 2010, p. 21).

Auxiliary variables are often used in occupational coding processes, as Table 2.4 shows for four surveys. For the EWCS coding quite a number of variables were used (Gallup Europe, 2010). The American Community Survey also uses a range of variables (Cheeseman Day, 2014). In contrast, Statistics Netherlands only uses the industry code, but they use extra survey questions to identify whether a respondent whose job title includes the word ‘manager’ has to be coded as a manager. Coding quality can be compared between coders by examining association with criterium (‘validation’) variables, such as: education, income and other occupations (Ganzeboom, 2014).

⁸ Note that Eurostat has not a centralised coding system for occupations for the European Labour Force Survey (ELFS). The ELFS is merged from national LFS datasets, which NSOs deliver to Eurostat in a described format.

Table 2.4 Auxiliary variables used to code occupations

Variable	ACS	ESS_ parental occs	EWCS	LFS_NL (EBB)
education level	1	1	1	
age	1			
geographic location	1			
income		1		
other occupations		1		
economic sector of employer			1	1
number of co-workers			1	
age when full time education was completed			1	
employment status			1	
private/public sector			1	
number of people working under the supervision of respondent			1	
MANAGERS ONLY Questions				1

Source ACS: Cheeseman Day (2014); ESS_parental occs: Ganzeboom (2014); EWCS: Gallup Europe (2010); EBB: Westerman and Offermans CBS (2014)

CASCOT and other classification software apply dictionary approaches for automatic occupational coding. Recently, machine learning algorithms such as naïve Bayes or k-nearest-neighbours appear to be a promising development, requiring a substantial amount of manually coded occupations to be used as training data for the automatic classification. To meet the demand for automatic coding in Germany, the IAB launched a project to apply machine learning algorithms to 300,000+ verbatim answers, which were manually coded with high quality.⁹ The project resulted in successful coding with this large scale training data. As Bethmann et al (2014) phrase it: ‘From a total survey error perspective this would free resources formerly spent on the reduction of processing error and offer the opportunity of employing those resources to reduce other error sources.’ The American Community Survey (ACS) uses a so-called occupation auto-coder, which is a set of logistic regression models, data dictionaries, and consistency edits (‘hardcodes’), developed from around two million manually coded records. The auto-coder assigns an occupation code if the quality score, based on agreement with clerk-coded records, is sufficiently high (Cheeseman Day, 2014). These automatic coding experiments are single-country operations. In Section 2.4 the design for a multi-country occupational auto-coder challenging high coding comparability across countries will be developed.

2.3 Methods for EU-wide measurement of occupations in web surveys

2.3.1 Introduction

This section details a method to facilitate the EU-wide measurement of occupations in web (CAWI), computer-assisted personal face-to-face (CAPI) and computer-assisted telephone (CATI) survey modes, using text string matching and search trees, and the requirements for the related look-up database. For the postal (PAPI) mode no other method than an open ended survey question is available, because this mode is not computer-assisted.

⁹ See <http://fdz.iab.de/339/section.aspx/Projektdetails/k140424305>, accessed 25 July 2014.

2.3.2 Closed versus open format survey questions about occupations

In PAPI, CATI or CAPI surveys, occupation is mostly asked in an open response format, followed by office coding, as discussed in Section 2.2. In contrast web surveys offer a unique possibility for a closed response format, using a search tree and text string matching. Web surveys allow for a choice-set of thousands of occupational titles, when using text string matching or a search tree for navigating through the choice-set.

For four reasons this method is advantageous over an open format question with office-coding. First, if designed well, the choice-set will consist only of occupations at the same level of aggregation. Second, unidentifiable occupational titles are absent. Third, field- or office-coding is not needed. Finally, in case of cross-country data-collections, survey operations and, in case of a multilingual database, the choice-set will be comparable across countries.

For four reasons this method is however disadvantageous. First, for respondents it is cognitive demanding to search their job title. This is particularly the case when using a search tree only, but less so when in addition a text string matching tool is used. With Google and other search engines so wide spread, text string matching has become a familiar activity for many respondents. Second, the choice-set is by definition incomplete and therefore some respondents may not find their job title or are unable to aggregate it into an occupational title. Third, it may be time-consuming for respondents to search for their job title. Finally, in mixed-mode surveys bias effects will occur when combining open format questions with closed format ones.

2.3.3 The very long tail of the occupational distribution

The stock of job titles is characterised by two features (Tijdens, 2014c). First, as said, the stock of job titles in a given country may easily exceed the 10,000s. Hardly any other survey question has such a large response set, probably with the exception of a survey question ‘What is the name of the company you work for’, because most countries will easily have 10,000s company names.

Second, the labour force is very unequal distributed over occupations, depicting a highly skewed distribution with a very long tail. Figure 2.1 shows how the Dutch labour force is distributed over 193 ISCO-08 3-digit occupational groups. For the look-up database of occupations this implies that it is important to identify the frequency of occupations. This enables the decisions which occupations should be included and which should not be included in the database. The stock of job titles is very dynamic over time and across countries, which requires regular updating of the database.

Figure 2.1 The distribution of the Netherlands labour force over 193 ISCO-08 3-digit occupational groups

Source CBS Statline, accessed 10 February 2014

2.3.4 The search tree

A search tree or an ‘iPod menu’ as it is sometimes called allows respondents to navigate the look-up table of occupations. The design requirements for search trees depend on the number of entries in the table, as Table 2.4 shows. A maximum for each step in the search tree is approximately 20, otherwise respondents will not comprehend the list easily. Hence, a 3-step search tree should not have more than 20*20*20=8,000 entries. Given the 10,000s of job titles, respondents will have to aggregate their job title into an occupational title. The search tree will facilitate them to find easily the aggregated occupation.

Table 2.5 Design requirements for search

# entries	Search tree structure	Example
<20 entries	1 list	<i>e.g.</i> education
20-400 entries	2 step search tree	<i>e.g.</i> industry
400-8,000 entries	3 step search tree	<i>e.g.</i> occupation

Source Tijdens (2014c)

The occupation search tree in the WageIndicator web survey has a 3-step structure, because it uses 1,700 occupational titles in its database. Figure 2.1 provides a screen shot of the search tree used in this web survey. The principles underlying its search tree and look-up database, such as the search paths, the alphabetic sorting, the skill levels, the corporate hierarchies, and readability issues, such as the wording of occupations and the translations have been explained elsewhere (Tijdens, 2010).

Figure 2.2 Search tree in the WageIndicator web survey

Source <http://www.paywizard.co.uk/main/pay/salariesurvey/salary-survey-employees>, accessed 8 Augustus 2014

2.3.5 The text string matching

Alternatively to a search tree, respondents in the WageIndicator web survey can use text string matching, as Figure 2.2 shows. The screenshot shows the text string matching in English and in Chinese.

Figure 2.3 Screenshots for text string matching in English and Chinese

Source <http://www.paywizard.co.uk/main/pay/salariesurvey/salary-survey-employees>, accessed 8 Augustus 2014 and <http://www.wageindicator.cn/main/salary/survey/employee-survey>, accessed 8 Augustus 2014

2.4 Design for an advanced, multi-country occupational coding tool

ISCO-08 defines a 4-digit classification for worldwide use and is available in English. Following its policy towards a harmonised occupational classification, the European Commission has translated the ISCO 4-digit classification into all languages of the European Union to ensure that occupations are coded similarly across countries.¹⁰ When it comes to the 5-digit occupations however, two approaches can be distinguished. The first one says that the ILO manual and descriptions are sufficiently detailed and hence it is assumed that national coding of 5-digit occupations leads to valid results across countries, hence that across countries comparable 5-digit occupations will be coded into the same 4-digit code. This method is applied in many multi-country surveys, where the field organisations code the occupations for the respective countries. The second approach states that only

¹⁰ See http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2009.292.01.0031.01.ENG, accessed 8 August 2014.

English occupational titles should be coded, and that therefore national job titles should be translated. This method is in part followed for the EWCS, as explained in Section 2.2 (Gallup Europe, 2010). In retrospect Ganzeboom (2014) in his effort to code parental occupations in the European Social Survey, applying the first approach, acknowledges that it would have been much better to ask the coders to translate the occupation files and then code all English titles, particularly because Google Translate has become a big help in this respect. It is not sure which approach is less costly. In the first approach the costs are related to the national coding, while no multi-country quality control can be applied. In the second approach translations might be costly, but central coding of the English occupations for the entire multi-country data collection is relatively cheap. In this proposal for a multi-country occupational coding tool, I follow the second approach and propose to translate all occupational titles in English.

As described in Section 2.2 a huge training set is required for an auto-coder to apply machine learning algorithms. Therefore, a major task consists of compiling a large volume, multilingual database of occupations, acting as the training set. This database falls apart into two components, one with individual level data, and one with occupation level data.

The first individual level database consists of merged and harmonised survey data from as many surveys as available. The merged dataset is harmonised for occupation codes and for the covariates industry, education, field of education, employment status, age, private/public sector, income, and other variables, and it has identifiers for survey name and version, survey mode, survey year, and occupational classification used.¹¹ Whenever available the text responses for the open format questions about job title, job description, and tasks should be included. To increase the body of text related to coded occupations, an open format job description question will be included in the 80-country WageIndicator web survey and the response to will be added to the database.

The second - occupation level - database consists of (a) all available coding indexes from National Statistical Offices (text and codes); (b) multilingual databases of occupational titles, preferably coded (text and codes); (c) job titles, job descriptions and task lists from a wide variety of sources, preferably with coded job titles (text and codes); (d) job titles, job descriptions and additional texts from vacancy databases such as EURES, Indeed and Monster, preferably with coded job titles (text and codes); (e) the millions of web visitors of the WageIndicator Jobs&Salary web pages will be asked to provide job descriptions and tasks in their job (these web visitors have identified their 4-digit occupation based on the web page); (f) as much as possible English translations of non-English job titles. A very first draft of the occupation level database is shown in Appendix 4 in Tjijens (2014c). Both databases will be used for the machine learning algorithms, while the individual level database will be used for the statistical analyses using auxiliary variables.

Once the two databases have enough content to act as a multi-country training set, next steps can be taken. For each country/language combination in the individual level database all verbatim job titles should be cleaned from misspellings, duplicates, abbreviations, replacement words such as ‘worker equals labourer’, alternative words, and plural job titles should be converted into singular one and female and male job titles should be harmonised. Per country rules have to be made for these cleaning activities. In this step crude job titles and job titles with multiple meaning such as manager, dealer, editor, and the phrasing of activities ‘engineering manager’ versus ‘engineer, managing a team’ should be identified and rules should be drafted for coding this ambiguous text. Then, all job titles should be translated in English, using available translations from the occupation level database or if absent from Google translate.

A next step includes the coding of all English job titles in the two databases into ISCO-08, using CASCOT. Then the initial codes can be compared to the CASCOT codes. Coding differences should be analysed and decision rules should be made to come to the final codes. In case the initial codes

¹¹ I propose to take the data dictionary of the WageIndicator web survey as the base file, particularly because this is a continuous survey, and hence every quarter new data will be added, whereas most other surveys are discrete surveys.

are in another classification than ISCO-08, crossover tables have to be applied. Next regression analyses for the probabilities of correct ISCO-08 4-digit codes should be ran. Finally the machine learning algorithms for occupational coding can be developed, including model estimates of the probability that the auto-coder agrees with the coding in the training set. If this functions well, the cleaning rules and the algorithms can be applied for office-coding of newly added datasets.

Once all job titles are correctly coded, for use in self-coding in web surveys and for interviewer coding in computer-assisted surveys a large, multi-country multilingual look-up database will become available. Using this database for each country the job title frequencies can be identified, needed for the selection of the items to be included in the search tree for web surveys. In the long run, this implies that for in web surveys the look-up table for text string matching is much larger than the items used in the search tree. A major challenge will be to apply the cleaning rules and algorithms for the self-identification in web surveys or for instant field-coding during an interview. No experience has been accumulated with auto- coding for these purposes. Further research is needed to develop this application.

3. The design of a tool for the measurement of occupations in web surveys using a global index of occupations

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3.1 Introduction

Occupation is a key variable in socio-economic research, used in a wide variety of studies. Where such studies use quantitative approaches, they usually rely on survey data. Measuring and coding of occupations is a major challenge for socio-economic surveys. Web surveys pose extra challenges. This section addresses specifically InGRID's Task 21.1.3 'Develop methods to facilitate the EU-wide measurement of occupations in web surveys' (Tijdens, 2015a). It builds on work done for the previous Section (Tijdens, 2014c) and on the discussions in the InGRID expert workshop 'Developing and testing new tools to measure occupations and their task and skill requirements', held 10-12 February 2014 in Amsterdam (see Section 5 in this report).

This Section details the design principles in the WISCO Database of Occupations_v2016. Section 3.2 sketches the history of the database. Section 3.3 provides an overview of the measurement and coding of occupations. Section 3.4 specifies the design for an occupations look-up table for semantic matching. Section 3.5 outlines further steps to be taken for the development of a database facilitating the EU-wide measurement of occupations in web surveys using an Application programming interface (API).

3.2 The history of the WISCO database of occupations

3.2.1 The start in 2000

In 2000, WageIndicator started in the Netherlands, aiming to collect up-to-date information about women's wage data by occupation. Hence, large sample sizes were needed. A volunteer survey was published in several women's magazines, resulting in almost 7,000 completed questionnaires. At the same time the survey was posted on a well-known women's website, resulting in more than 7,000 questionnaires. In the print survey the 55 most frequent occupations were listed, clustered into seven groups with an option 'other' at the bottom of each group. The reasons for the choice in favour of a predefined list instead of a text box were related to the data-entry costs. In the web survey, this list took the form of 2-level search tree, including an option 'other' which was followed by an open text. Slightly over one quarter of the respondents used the text box to enter a job title not listed, which were recoded into 19 additional occupational titles (Tijdens, 2001).

In 2001, WageIndicator started its own website, presenting a Salary Check for women, based on the survey data. The web survey was posted on the website and visitors were invited to complete the survey, which was now addressing both women and men. For the occupation question, a two level search listing the most frequent occupations for men as well as the 55 plus the 19 additional women's

occupations, resulting in 105 occupational titles (Tijdens *et al*, 2002). These titles were coded according to the Standard Occupational Classification from Statistics Netherlands.

3.2.2 The WOLIWEB and EurOccupations projects

In 2004, as part of the EU-funded WOLIWEB project (EU-FP6, no 506590), WageIndicator could start websites with continuous web surveys on work and wages in another seven countries, at that time the largest in the European Union. Again the choice was in favour of a predefined list with a search tree and not in favour of post-coding text strings, due to budgetary considerations. To populate the list of occupations, project partners were asked to send coding indexes or other lists of occupations from their countries, and preferably provide an English translation of the titles. The list of English titles was named the source list. By 2006, the database contained in total more than 5,000 occupational titles, many of them present in one language and in English. Occupations from different countries with the same English occupational title were merged. For most countries the database included a list of 500 to 1500 occupations. The aggregation level of the occupational titles varied across the countries, including both very broad and very narrow titles. Where possible, the titles in the source list were coded ISCO-88, otherwise they received a follow-up number. In 2005 and 2006, some countries added occupational titles to the list, based on feedback from web visitors who could not identify their occupation. The search tree in the web survey was extended from 2 to 3 levels.

In 2006, the EurOccupations project (EU-FP6, no 028987) allowed to adapt and modify the database. Based on Draft 3 of ISCO-08, published in September 2006 (ILO, 2006), and on ILO's Alphabetical index of occupational titles for ISCO-88(COM), the source list was revised and coded according to ISCO-08. This resulted in a source list with 1,433 occupational titles. If translations were not available in the database, the occupations were translated for the languages of the eight EU countries in the project. Since 2007/Q2, the list was implemented in the WageIndicator web survey, using a three level search tree. In spring 2008, ILO published the final draft ISCO-08 classification with 433 occupational titles at 4-digit level.¹² Compared to Draft 3, a number of occupations was assigned a different skill level. The codes in our source list of occupations were adapted accordingly. Meanwhile, the WageIndicator partners in non-EurOccupations countries had commented the source list, noticing translation difficulties and adding missing occupational titles. The source list was extended and critically reviewed with regard to internal consistency and suitability within the search tree of the web survey. Early 2009, the source list included 1,594 distinct occupational titles with translations for approximately 30 languages for almost 50 countries in and outside Europe. The database was renamed the World Database of ISCO Occupations (WISCO). The primary aim of the WISCO Database of Occupations was its use for valid self-identification of occupation in web surveys by means of a search tree (Tijdens, 2010).

3.2.3 The search tree and semantic matching

In 2009, the revised WISCO Database of Occupations was uploaded in the WageIndicator web survey for all countries. Data collection started for some countries as of July 2009, but for most countries as of October 2009. The database and the search tree were also implemented in the Salary Checks in most of the 50 countries with a WageIndicator website at that time. With millions of web visitors and over a hundred thousand respondents per year, the search tree and the occupation database were tested extensively. Web visitors and survey respondents send relatively few emails to WageIndicator about the occupations, pointing to a satisfactory search tree and the related list of occupations.

¹² The final ISCO-08 coding index was published in 2012 (ILO, 2012).

In the years after 2009, occupations have been added to the database, mostly because web visitors requested so in their emails. For the UK, a number of management occupations and for the Czech Republic and Slovakia medical specialists have been added and for Germany the skill levels for some skilled occupations have been further detailed by distinguishing occupations at university and higher vocational level. By 2015, the database held between 1,896 occupational titles, of which 132 were country specific. Apart from the latter 132, almost all titles were translated in the 43 languages of the WageIndicator websites and web surveys. The number of occupational titles varied slightly across countries, because in some countries some occupation titles could not be translated or distinct occupational titles in the source list were translated similarly. Figure 3.1 shows a cut out of the database.

Figure 3.1 Screenshot of the 2015 WISCO database of occupations

1	ISCO0813	Master label	am_ET	ar	az_AZ	ba_ID
2	110010000000	Commissioned officer armed forces	የጦር ኃይሎች ባለሙያዎች መኮንን	ضابط في القوات المسلحة	Harbi qüvvələrin zabiti	Perwira angkatan darat
3	110020000000	Military operations leader	የጦር ኃይሎች ዘመቻዎች ጠቅላይ	قائد العمليات العسكرية	Harbi əməliyyatların rəhbəri	Pimpinan operasi militer
4	111101000000	Member of parliament, legislator	የፓርላማ አባል፣ የአዎንታዊ አወጣጥ	عضو في البرلمان ، مشرع	Parlament üzvü	Pembuat undang-undang
5	111102000000	Mayor, alderman		العمدة ، رئيس مجلس بلدي	Mer, icra hakimiyyatının başkanı	Mayor, anggota dewan kota
6	111113000000	City councillor, county councillor	የከተማ ምክር ቤት አባል፣ የጊዮ ምክር ቤት አባል	عضو مجلس محلي أو القروي / بلدية	Şəhər şura üzvü, Region şurası	Anggota dewan kota
7	111202000000	Public administration manager	የአገልግሎት አስተዳደር ማኅደር	مدير الإدارة العامة	Administrasiya rəisi, dövlət xidməti rəisi	Manajer administrasi publik
8	111203000000	Senior non-legislative official	ከፍተኛ ስልጣን አወጣጥ ያልሆኑ ባለሙያዎች	كبار المسؤولين الحكوميين من غير	Qeyri-dövlət müəssisəsinin rəhbəri	Pejabat senior bukan pembuat undang-undang
9	111204000000	Senior government official	ከፍተኛ የጠቅላይ ስልጣን ባለሙያዎች	مسؤول حكومي كبير	Dövlət müəssisəsinin işçisi	Pejabat senior pemerintahan
10	111206000000	Diplomat	ዲፕሎማት	دبلوماسي	Diplomat	Diplomat
11	111301000000	Traditional chief or head of village	ባሕላዊ አለቃ ወይም የጠቅላይ ስልጣን አወጣጥ	العمدة أو رئيس القرية	Kənd sovetinin nümayəndəsi	Kepala kampung/suku
12	111401000000	Employers' organisation official	የግራም ስርዓት ጠቅላይ ስልጣን አወጣጥ	مسؤول منظمة أرباب العمل	Məşğulluq xidməti nümayəndəsi	Pejabat senior organisasi pengurusan
13	111402000000	Humanitarian organisation official	የሰላም ጥያቄ ስርዓት ጠቅላይ ስልጣን አወጣጥ	مسؤول منظمة إنسانية	Humanitar yardım təşkilatının rəhbəri	Pejabat senior organisasi kemanusiaan
14	111403000000	Political party official	የፖለቲካ ፓርቲ ባለሙያዎች	مسؤول / الأحزاب السياسية	Siyasi partiya nümayəndəsi	Pejabat senior partai politik

Note: The first column shows the ISCO-08 code (first 4-digits are the ISCO code); the second column shows the source label, the remaining columns show the translations for Amharic, Arabic, Azeri and Indonesian.

In 2012, the search tree in the web survey and the Salary Check was extended with a semantic matching tool (Figure 3.2). Semantic matching allows visitors to self-identify their occupation by typing text whereby matches with words in the list of occupations for their particular language are instantly shown. Visitors can then select the most relevant match. The tool is used in the WageIndicator web survey (Figure 2.3) and in the WageIndicator Salary Check (Figure 3.2). In the year 2016, almost half a million web visitors self-identified their occupation through the search tree or the autosuggest.

Figure 3.2 Screenshot for the tool to self-identify occupation with a search tree and with autosuggest

Source WageIndicator Salary Check for Great Britain, <http://wageindicator.co.uk/main/pay/salarycheck>, accessed 15 December 2015.

Although 1,600 occupational titles may seem a large number, one has to take into account that a labour market in any country can easily include 10,000 or more job titles. The use of the database for self-identification in web surveys would therefore profit from extending the number of occupations as well as from further testing of the database. In 2014, the InGRID project provided funding for the design of a tool for the measurement of occupations in web surveys using a global index of

occupations. In 2015, the SERISS project (EU-Horizon 2020, no 654221) provided funding to populate the database, according to the design principles outlined here, to 5,000 titles and to more countries/languages, and to develop an Application programming interface (API) for the measurement of occupations in web surveys.

3.3 Overview: classifying and measuring occupations

3.3.1 Classifying occupations

In 1958, the International Labour Office (ILO) of the United Nations had developed the International Standard of Occupational Classification (ISCO) to harmonise the measurement of occupations, with revisions in 1968, 1988, and 2008. Today, ISCO has become the standard classification in many countries for their Labour Force Surveys or Censuses. ISCO-08, as was the case for its predecessors, defines a job as a set of work tasks and duties performed by one person. Jobs with the same set of main tasks and duties are aggregated into the so-called 4-digit occupation units. On the basis of similarity in the tasks and duties performed, the units are grouped into 3- and 2-digit groups, which in turn on the basis of the skill level are grouped into 1-digit groups (Hunter, 2014). ISCO distinguishes four skill levels, notably unskilled, semi-skilled, skilled and highly skilled, which are related to ISCED, the International Standard Classification of Education (ILO, 2012).

ILO's ISCO classification and coding index assume that occupations with the same titles are classified similarly across countries, otherwise there would not be an argument for a global classification. Hence, the database of occupations challenges whether occupations with the same title are similar across countries. This applies to same languages in different countries, but even more so to different languages in different countries. The answer is that we don't know and that we have neither the methods nor the means to test empirically whether the statement is true. Within the EurOccupations project as well as in the Eduworks and Ingrid projects empirical tests have been undertaken to measure the heterogeneity of tasks within occupations (Tijdens, De Ruijter, De Ruijter, 2012; Tijdens, De Ruijter, De Ruijter, 2014; Visintin *et al.*, 2015). The results show that the frequencies of a given set of tasks within each occupation vary largely within and across countries. This challenges research of occupational boundaries within and across countries, but such studies are beyond the scope of this paper.

ISCO-08 defines a 4-digit classification for worldwide use and is available in English. Following its policy towards a harmonised occupational classification, the European Commission (2009) has translated the ISCO 4-digit classification into all languages of the European Union to ensure that occupations are coded similarly across countries.¹³ When it comes to classifying 5-digit occupations however, two approaches can be distinguished. The first one says that the ILO manual and descriptions are sufficiently detailed and hence it is assumed that national coding of 5-digit occupations leads to valid results across countries. This method is applied in many multi-country surveys, where the field organisations code the occupations for their respective countries. The second approach states that only English occupational titles should be coded, and that therefore national job titles should be translated and then coded according to the English title. For three countries (Albania, Kosovo and Montenegro) this method is followed for Eurofound's European Working Conditions Survey 2010 WCS: the verbatim responses were translated in English to facilitate central quality control (Gallup Europe, 2010). In retrospect Ganzeboom (2014), applying the first approach in his effort to code parental occupations in the European Social Survey, acknowledges that it would have been much better to ask the coders to translate the occupation titles in English and then code these. Ganzeboom states that particularly because Google Translate has become a big help in this respect. It is not sure which approach is less costly. In the first approach the costs are related to the national coding, while

¹³ See http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=uriserv:OJ.L_.2009.292.01.0031.01.ENG, accessed 8 August 2014.

no multi-country quality control can be applied. In the second approach translations might be costly, but central coding of the English occupations for the entire multi-country data collection is relatively cheap. In this proposal for a multi-country occupational coding tool, the second approach will be followed and all occupational titles will be translated in English.

Many statistical offices and survey agencies have developed coding indexes and related coding tools to facilitate office coding of the raw text from an open ended survey question about respondent's occupation. A well-known coding tool is CASCOT, an abbreviation of Computer Assisted Structured Coding Tool. CASCOT is a computer program designed to make the coding of text information to standard classifications simpler, quicker and more reliable. It is developed and maintained by the Warwick Institute for Employment Research of the University of Warwick in Great Britain. CASCOT is available for coding occupations in nine languages, notably Dutch, English, Finnish, French, German, Italian, Portuguese, Slovak, and Spanish.¹⁴ In the USA and in Germany auto-coders are developed (Cheeseman Day, 2014; Bethmann *et al*, 2014). A huge training set of coded responses is required to apply machine learning algorithms.

These tools for office coding consist of an index for coding the verbatim responses plus a set of rules, that indicate which phrases are redundant, for example the words 'I work as a'. The rules also may identify the most common typing errors, may remove other superfluous or irrelevant text, and apply extra checks for aggregated or vague occupations. CASCOT and the auto-coders can identify to what extent the raw text matches an occupational title in the coding index. For automatic coding, for example in CASCOT, the thresholds of 80 or 70% can be set to accept the match as a valid code.

3.3.2 Measuring occupations in web surveys

3.3.2.1 Open versus closed questions in web surveys

Web surveys challenge the measurement of occupations. As discussed in Section 2, in other survey modes an open question can be applied. It is likely however that the response is less reliable than in other survey modes. In contrast to other surveys modes, an interviewer cannot correct odd responses. In addition, web surveys elicit more often odd responses than I've noticed in printed surveys. In the anonymity of the Internet, responses such as 'None of your business' and worse are given. Compared to other survey modes, web surveys however allow for self-identification using extensive look-up tables. Surveys with a mixed mode approach face difficult choices here, but surveys that are solely based on the web mode can explore the look-up tables. Note that both web surveys and self-identification assume respondents' reading skills and therefore poses high demands on readability of the look-up tables.

Web surveys allow for self-identification using a look-up database. This database however needs contain a large number of entries to satisfy the large majority of respondents, given labour markets of 10,000 or more occupational titles and given a skewed distribution of jobholders over occupations. The content of the database will be discussed in the Section 4. In web surveys, three techniques facilitate searching a look-up table. First, an alphabetically sorted drop-down list can be used. Second, a search tree with two or three levels can be used. Third, an open format question with semantic matching can be used. All three will be discussed hereafter.

'Don't know' answers are rarely given to the question about occupation and therefore I assume that almost all respondents know their job title. They tend to report a detailed job title, as they know it from their employment contract, job classification scheme, collective bargaining agreement, job advertisement, or just from a common understanding in the workplace. Moreover, respondents are able to aggregate their job title in an occupational title, if different from the job title, because the occupational title is used in labour market communication, for example in educational trajectories or

¹⁴ See <http://www2.warwick.ac.uk/fac/soc/ier/software/cascot/internat/>, accessed 17 December 2015.

job ads. Hence, once presented a list of occupational titles, respondents will recognise that their occupational title is asked and not their job title, and they will be able to aggregate their job title into their occupational title.

Scrolling is typically applied to exhaustive tables that contain well defined and general understood words. Scrolling assumes that these words can be sorted alphabetically in a commonly understood way. Due to readability considerations scrolling requires a database with not too many entries, typically at most a few hundred entries. A list of countries can be searched perfectly by means of an alphabetically sorted scroll list, allowing web visitors to easily identify their country of choice from a list of approximately 250 items. Couper presents another example, notably a list of drugs (Couper *et al.*, 2012).

Can scrolling be applied for self-identification of occupation? Occupational titles are not standardised and hence the occupational titles air-conditioning mechanic and mechanic air-conditioning are used interchangeably. For the alphabetic sorting in a scroll list however this requires multiple entries for ne occupational titles. Given that the look-up table preferably holds thousands of entries, the requirement of multiple entries enlarges the table substantially. Therefore, it must be concluded that scrolling is not an appropriate technique for respondent's self-identification of occupation in web surveys.

A search tree or an 'iPod menu', as it is sometimes called, allows visitors to navigate through a look-up table. Typically a search tree is used for nested items, such as cities within provinces, whereby only one search path leads to a city. Search trees commonly have two levels, but can have three. Each level within the search tree preferably should be sorted alphabetically to facilitate respondents' understanding of the tree. Additionally, a search tree requires that the parent entries are phrased in a commonly understood, unambiguous way. Note that, although the ISCO classification is a hierarchical system, it is designed for classification purposes and not for the purpose of self-identification. Hence, the classification does not provide the content for a search tree.

When the WageIndicator web survey started in 2001, the survey used a search tree for the self-identification of occupation, as explained in Section 2. For such self-identification a search tree was the only possibility, because at that time the semantic matching technique was not available for web surveys. Moreover, web visitors used a desktop to visit the website and to complete the survey. For reasons of readability on a desktop screen, the number of entries in each level of the search tree was maximised to at most 20 entries, and hence the total number of entries in the look-up table was maximised with at most 20 entries in the 1st level, $20*20=400$ entries in the 2nd level and $20*20*20=8,000$ entries in the 3rd level. Given that quite some occupational titles had to be placed on more than one search path, the total number of entries was much lower. In 2001, the look-up table in the Netherlands comprised of less than 400 occupational titles, and therefore the search tree could cope with two levels. In the following years the number of occupations grew and the search tree had to be expanded to three levels.

For respondents it is cognitive demanding and time consuming to navigate through such an extensive search tree, and does therefore result in partial drop-out (Tijdens, 2014a). To find a solution for the dilemma between the growing number of occupational titles in the database and the need to reduce the number of entries in the search tree, occupations with presumably few jobholders were not included, although an empirical underpinning of the distribution of jobholders over a 5-digit occupations was lacking. Additionally, to reduce entries similar occupational titles were merged into one entry in the 3rd level, because the search path was the same for similar job titles and respondents would recognise similar occupational titles as their own. Third level entries included occupational titles such as:

- carpenter, joiner;
- goldsmith, silversmith;
- city councillor, county councillor;

- clown, acrobat, magician, hypnotist;

Semantic matching is typically applied in cases where the list of items is not exhaustive and the phrasing of the search term is fuzzy. Google Search is a well-known example of searching with semantic matching. For self-identification of occupations, semantic matching is probably the best solution, but it requires an exhaustive look-up list in order to provide matches for the vast majority of respondents. Hence, the look-up table used in the search tree should be extended and the merged occupational titles should be unmerged into one entry per occupational title. Section 4 explains the underlying principles used for the source list.

Google Search can cope with typing errors by suggesting ‘Do you mean xxx’? Currently the semantic matching tool in the WageIndicator web survey cannot cope with typing errors, as Figure 3.3 shows. I assume that respondents will correct their text when no matches show up, or that they will use the search tree. It may well be the case that in the foreseeable future the tool can provide suggestions, but this will not be implemented in this stage.

Figure 3.3 Screenshot showing that a typing error does not provide a match

Source WageIndicator Salary Check for Great Britain, <http://wageindicator.co.uk/main/pay/salarycheck>, accessed 15 December 2015

In an overview of 25 surveys with an open-ended question about occupation, 14 ask for a job description (Tijdens, 2014c). This is the so-called tasks-and-duties-question, and is typically asked for office coding purposes, notably when the answer to the occupation question cannot be coded. The phrasing of the question varied largely across the surveys.

From 2015 onwards, the WageIndicator web survey respondents are asked to provide a description of their job. Respondents are asked so after having identified their 5-digit occupation with the semantic matching tool. The tasks-and-duties responses will be used to identify the reliability of the selected 5-digit occupation.

3.4 Design requirements of a database for semantic matching

3.4.1 Introduction

This section details the design requirements for a database to facilitate respondents' self-identification of occupation by means of semantic matching in web surveys.¹⁵ It discusses the principles underlying the design of the database, including a review of problems to be solved. Table 3.2 presents the main concepts used in this section.

¹⁵ The database may also serve for interviewer identification of respondents' occupations in computer-assisted personal face-to-face (CAPI) and computer-assisted telephone (CATI) survey modes. This is predominantly a technical challenge and therefore beyond the scope of this paper. For the postal (PAPI) mode no other method than an open ended survey question is available, because this mode is not computer-assisted.

Table 3.1 The main concepts used in this section

Source list	The list of all occupations in the database, in English
Code	The ISCO-08 codes of the source list
Locale	The combination of language and country, for example en_US and es_US
Translation	The translation of an occupational title in the source list to the language of the respective locale
Look-up table	The list shown to the survey respondent, depending of the locale of the survey
Database	The joint source list, codes and translations
Entry	One occupational title in a look-up table

A coding tool for office coding is typically designed for high volume batch coding and providing a certainty score per coded verbatim. For a semantic matching tool in web surveys, this application is irrelevant. Here, the purpose of the database is to provide each respondent with a list of matches for a choice of his/her most relevant occupational title. The database aims to generate responses at 4-digit level of the ISCO-08 classification and to prevent responses at 1-, 2-, or 3-digit level and to prevent unidentifiable responses.

3.4.2 Drafting and coding the source list

Given that a national labour market easily can consist of 10,000 or more occupational titles and given that the distribution of jobholders over these occupational titles is extremely skewed, it will be impossible to draft an exhaustive database of all occupational titles. For an open-ended survey question with office coding this implies that every survey includes respondents in rare occupations which have not been reported and hence not coded in previous surveys. In case of self-identification with semantic matching these respondents probably will try the titles of adjacent occupations. Nevertheless, to meet the demand the source list should include as many occupations as possible.

As discussed in Section 2, for a web survey with self-identification by means of a search tree the number of occupational titles in the source list is limited, but this technical constraint does not hold for semantic matching. Hence, the source list can be very large. Given time and budget restrictions however, we decided to depart from the ISCO-08 coding index with almost 7,000 occupational titles (ILO, 2012). This database includes however duplicate titles.¹⁶

A two-step procedure will be followed for the design of the source list. In a first step only 5-digit occupational titles with reliable ISCO-08 coding will be included. These are found in three sources:

1. the more than 6,000 occupational titles in the ISCO-08 Index EN May 2013 final draftAWcoding index, controlled for duplicates (English only);
2. the more than 1,700 occupational titles of the WISCO database (English + translations);
3. the occupational titles in the ISCO-08 coding indexes of 18 national statistical offices in not-English speaking countries.¹⁷ These coding indexes are in national languages and will be translated to English, using Google Translate and checked by a skilled translator. Typically coding indexes apply reverse word order, to facilitate office coding. For inclusion in the database the words will be changed into the right order.

In a next step, all English occupational titles will be checked for duplicates. Hence, if an occupation from the Spanish and one from the Latvian indexes are translated to the same English occupational title, they will be one title in the source list with the same ISCO-08 code. If this occupational title is

¹⁶ Note that the SERISS project aimed to enlarge the database to 5,000 titles.

¹⁷ Albania, Austria, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Italy, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovak Republic, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Turkey.

not present in the coding indexes of the other countries, it will be translated to the respective languages. To increase the comparability of occupations across countries, translations by national labour market experts are preferred over translations by professional translators, and national used occupational titles are preferred over literal translations. Note that even in countries with the same language the same occupations may have different titles. Therefore, each locale has its own look-up table.

Once all above mentioned lists are entered in the database, the coding needs to be checked for consistency. For example, if the occupations from the Spanish and the Latvian indexes are translated in the same English occupational title, but have been coded differently by the Spanish respectively Latvian statistical office, a final check is required. Either a translation is not correct and therefore should not be considered the same occupation, or the same occupation was coded differently in any of the coding indexes. Hence, the translations and the codes should be checked. For the latter we propose to use the CASCOT coding tool to decide about the code.

Once the database drafted in the first step is satisfactory, other lists of occupations from non-English speaking countries will be considered for adding to the database. These may be lists with or without an ISCO-08 code. If an occupation from a list is not yet present in the look-up table of the country at stake, it will be translated in English and checked if adding the occupation makes sense. Among others, the following lists will be considered:

1. the database of licensed occupations in the European Union;
2. the database of occupations included in the WageIndicator Collective Agreements Database and Minimum Wage Database in Africa, Asia and Latin America;
3. a database of 300 occupations which were translated from English in several Slavic languages
4. the ESCO occupation database;
5. a file with translated university positions;
6. lists of occupations for languages not yet available from the coding indexes such as Japanese or Arabic.

The resulting source list may include more than 7,000 occupational titles, and each look-up table will probably include 4,000 or more titles. Note that it occurs regularly that two distinct titles in English are translated to one title in a foreign language, thereby reducing the size of the look-up table for that language.

To ensure high quality coding, for each locale its look-up table of course needs to include at least one 5-digit occupational title in each ISCO-08 4-digit occupational unit. However, in case of office coding unidentifiable occupations are usually classified in the appropriate residual 4-digit occupational category, called ‘not elsewhere classified’, for example Unit Group 1349 ‘Professional Services Managers Not Elsewhere Classified’. ISCO-08 4-digit has 27 residual units. Luckily, ILO (2012) lists examples of occupational titles classified in the residual units. The database includes these occupational titles, and hence all ISCO-08 4-digit units have at least one entry in the source list and in the look-up tables.

3.4.3 Male versus female titles

In some countries male and female occupational titles are different, whereas in other countries only gender-neutral or male occupational titles are in use. For example for Germany, the English word DTP operator is translated to DTP operator for men and DTP operatorin for women. The vast majority of German occupational titles have distinct words for males and females. Even in English, a few female and male occupational titles are distinguished, for example actor and actress or waiter and waitress. In a search tree, for readability reasons the occupational titles should be brief and easy to understand, and therefore feminine occupational titles had to be restricted to a minimum. In the semantic matching database, however, it is easy to include a so-called gender filter and the look-up

table should include columns for male and female occupational titles. Hence, the look-up table does not include an occupation Watchman/woman, but a male occupation Watchman and a female occupation Watchwoman. If the respondent's gender is female, the matching results from the female column will be shown, if present. Otherwise, the male/neutral titles from the look-up table will be shown. If the respondent's gender is not known, the male titles will be shown.

3.4.4 Start year and end year

Occupational structures are dynamic and the occupational composition of a labour force varies over time and across countries. Due to technological and organisational changes, new and emerging occupations arise. Most surveys ask respondents for their current occupation, but some have questions about father's and mother's occupation, mostly specified as the occupation when respondent was 14 years of age. Other surveys address elderly people, who are no longer in paid employment, but are asked to report their last occupation before retirement. This challenges the identification of time frames for the occupational titles. A straddle carrier driver or a web manager did not exist in periods when the straddle carrier or the web was not yet introduced. Therefore a start year can be assigned to an occupation in the source list. Hence, start years do not vary across countries. Of course, start years are only assigned to those occupations where this is known, for example in the case of web managers, where the start year 1985 is assigned.

The dynamic occupational structure also points to obsolete occupations, challenging the assignment of an end year to occupations in the look-up table. The database of historical occupations HISCO does include occupational titles that don't exist today, because the machinery, equipment or materials used have become outdated. The HISCO scheme is based on the coding of the 1,000 most frequent male and female occupational titles in datasets from eight different countries: Belgium, Britain, Canada, France, Germany, the Netherlands, Norway and Sweden.¹⁸ The occupational data which were employed to develop the scheme span the period 1690-1970, but are mostly from the nineteenth century. The HISCO database is not intended to be included in the look-up table, but whenever a need arises to do so, it could easily be done. Whenever an occupation in the database is obviously outdated, an end year will be assigned.

3.4.5 Highly aggregated job titles: clerks, operators or teachers

From office coding it is well-known that some respondents tend to report a highly aggregated job title such as clerk, operator or teacher. These titles are too aggregated to be classified at a 4-digit level. Typically, surveys with open text field provide instructions to prevent this problem. In the database, these highly aggregated occupational titles are therefore not included. If respondents key in 'teacher', they are offered a choice of many teaching occupations, and similarly when they key in 'clerk', as Figure 3.4 shows. Similarly, no entries for highly aggregated occupational titles such as 'manager' or 'shopkeeper'. The database holds only specific titles.

¹⁸ See <https://socialhistory.org/en/projects/hisco-history-work>, accessed 15 December 2015.

Figure 3.4 Screenshot showing the match list for highly aggregated occupations

Source WageIndicator Salary Check for Great Britain, <http://wageindicator.co.uk/main/pay/salarycheck>, accessed 15 December 2015

3.4.6 Abbreviations and organisation specific job titles

In work organisations, people may use abbreviations or very specific words for their job title. As it is impossible to trace these abbreviated job titles across countries, the database does not include these very specific job titles. They do not provide a match, challenging the respondent to key in a related occupational title, as Figure 3.5 shows.

Figure 3.5 Screenshot showing that an abbreviation does not provide a match

Source WageIndicator Salary Check for Great Britain, <http://wageindicator.co.uk/main/pay/salarycheck>, accessed 15 December 2015

3.4.7 Synonyms

Some occupations have one or more synonym titles. As much as possible, these titles will be included in the look-up tables, because survey respondents may search on either synonym. For example, the occupations barber, hairdresser, and hairstylist are all included in the English look-up table for the United Kingdom. In other countries, the three occupational titles would possibly be translated to one title. In those cases they are only once present in that look-up table and they are assigned the 5-digit code of the most generic term of the synonyms. Synonym occupational titles will have different 5-digit codes, but the same 4-digit code. Note that a look-up table for semantic matching cannot assign two different codes to the same occupational title. Hence, for each language the look-up table consists of unique titles only. Some occupational titles can be written in reverse order. An example is *Cleaner aircraft* and *Aircraft cleaner*. In case of semantic matching both ways facilitate matching. In these cases the look-up tables will therefore include one entry only.

One could consider slang words for occupations as synonyms. For example the word wig picker is slang for psychiatrist. However, slang words are not included in the database and respondents will not be provided with a match, as Figure 3.6 shows. These respondents will understand that they need to enter another word or use the search tree.

Figure 3.6 Screenshot showing that a slang word does not provide a match

Source WageIndicator Salary Check for Great Britain, <http://wageindicator.co.uk/main/pay/salarycheck>, accessed 15 December 2015

3.4.8 Skill levels, professionals, associate professionals and certified occupations

ISCO-08 distinguishes four skill levels, referring to the ISCED educational categories (ILO 2012). An occupation’s required skill level is the basis of ISCO’s skill level structure. This challenges measurement difficult issues that have to be solved in the source list of the database, as will be discussed here.

A first issue is that ISCO uses the words professional and associate professional to distinguish between the highly skilled and the skilled professionals. Using the semantic matching respondents will definitely not use these words to indicate their occupation. This challenges the source list to phrase occupational titles such that respondents will assess their appropriate skill level. For example, the word engineer is used only for highly skilled occupations, the word technician is used for skilled occupations and the word mechanic for semi-skilled. But even if these words are replaced by more commonly understood occupational titles, how will a respondent select between a Ship engineering technician (major group 3) and a Ship engineer (major group 2), because they both provide a match on the search term ‘ship engineer’? One solution can be to default classify these occupations in major group 3 and add a follow-up question about the occupation’s required educational level according to the ISCED classification to decide whether the respondent should be classified in major group 2.

Another solution is to include a reference to the required education. In the Netherlands, for example, the associate nurse is distinguished from the professional nurse because the occupational title includes a reference to the required education, notably ‘verpleegkundige (mbo)’ and ‘verpleegkundige (hbo)’ [nurse with medium vocational training and nurse with higher vocational training]. In Belgium, as learned from the EurOccupations expert, only one nurse occupation does exist. Therefore, the look-up table will not include an occupation title for the Nursing associate professional for Belgium (Table 3.3). Of course, this approach is based on country-level information, which obviously will not be available for all countries at stake. In these cases the database will include the translated occupational titles.

Table 3.2 Code, source list and two look-up tables for two occupational titles

Code	Source list	nl_NL	nl_BE
22210100	Hospital nurse	Verpleegkundige (hbo)	Verpleegkundige
32210100	Nursing associate professional	Verpleegkundige (mbo)	-

A second issues relates to the fact that within countries and within ISCO skill levels, occupations can refer to distinct ISCED levels. In Germany, for example, the ‘Archivar/in, Diplom (FH)’ is distinct from the ‘Archivar/in, Diplom (Uni)’ [Archivist with Higher Education diploma and Archivist with University diploma]. Similar problems may arise for the engineers, a large group in most countries. The following solution is proposed, whereby the Archivist is not present in the German translation, and Archivar/in, Diplom (FH) and (Uni) are not present in all other translations (Table 3.4).

Table 3.3 Code, source list and three look-up tables for six occupational titles

Code	Source list	en_UK	de_DE	nl_NL
26210100	Archivist	Archivist	-	Archivaris
26210101	Archivist (HEd)	-	Archivar/in, Diplom (FH)	
26210102	Archivist (Uni)	-	Archivar/in, Diplom (Uni)	
21410100	Industrial engineer	Industrial engineer	Ingenieur	-
21410101	Industrial engineer (Uni)	-	-	Ingenieur (wo)
21410102	Industrial engineer (HEd)	-	-	Ingenieur (hbo)

A third issue relates to the distinction between licensed or certified and non-licensed occupations, such as the Accountant, as shown in Table 4.1. For EU countries, the database of licensed occupations will be used to identify the licensed occupations. For non-EU countries licensed occupations will be added if reported.

Table 3.4 Code, source list and two look-up tables for six occupational titles

Code	Source list	nl_NL	en_UK
24110100	Accountant	-	Accountant (unqualified)
24110102	Accountant (Uni)	Register-accountant (RA)	-
24110103	Accountant (chartered)	-	Accountant (chartered)
24110104	Accountant (HEd)	Accountant, administratieconsulent (AA)	-

3.4.9 Occupations in the corporate hierarchy

Large and medium-sized organisations usually have a well-developed division of work, shaping hierarchical demarcation lines between occupations. For several reasons, issues related to the corporate hierarchy have to be solved in the database. First, ISCO-08 has assigned different skill levels to different positions within the hierarchy. Second, respondents prefer to report their position within the hierarchy. Third, valid self-identification assumes that occupational titles are clear with respect to their position in the corporate hierarchy. Several features of the corporate hierarchy are discussed here.

Many respondents prefer to indicate the hierarchy within their occupation by adding words such as senior or junior. It requires substantive empirical work to conclude for which occupations these levels are applicable and for which they are not, and this may vary across countries. Therefore, the source list does not include separate entries for junior or senior variations of an occupational title. The same applies to respondents reporting to be the 1st, 2nd or 3rd cook, pilot, or other occupational titles, and to the word 'all-round'. The matching algorithms will disregard these additions. In the WageIndicator web survey respondents are offered a follow-up survey question where these categories can be ticked, if desired.

Respondents also prefer to indicate when they occupy a supervisory position. ISCO-08 classifies supervisors in the same unit group as the most skilled workers supervised, while department managers are classified in major group 1 Managers. For survey respondents, the boundaries between the

two groups may not be too clear, valid coding requires that they are perceived to be distinct. Therefore, the database includes long lists of first line supervisors and department managers, such as:

- first line supervisor front-office tellers;
- first line supervisor office clerks;
- first line supervisor back-office clerks;
- first line supervisor police inspectors or Detectives;
- first line supervisor food preparation workers;
- technical department manager;
- engineering department manager;
- manufacturing department manager;
- financial department manager;
- personnel department manager.

The coding should be tested against the answers to the firm size question and against the question about supervisory position and number of persons supervised. A set of rules will be developed to modify the respondent's code when these tests yield unreliable combinations.

The concepts of careering, job ladders and job-enlargement blur the demarcation lines across occupations, whereas clarity is critical for valid self-identification. In the EurOccupations project this turned out most problematic for the assistant occupations (Tijdens, 2010). Is the assistant plumber part of a job ladder to become a plumber and thus one occupation, or are both separate occupations? This will vary worldwide and therefore in the source list the word assistant has been avoided as much as possible and replaced with the word helper.

3.4.10 Composite jobs

Small organisations tend to employ workers in composite jobs. Respondents may therefore want to classify themselves in more than one occupation. Web surveys using search trees have two solutions to this problem. The first solution includes an instruction to the survey question that the occupation should be selected on which most time is spend. The second solution is allowing respondents to tick more than one occupation. Unfortunately, due to technical constraints the WageIndicator web survey does not facilitate a second choice, but may do so in the years to come.

3.4.11 Handicraft workers and machine-operators

In the cause of the 20th century, small-scale workshops have been replaced by factories and craft occupations by machine-operators due to industrialisation and technological innovations. Countries vary with respect to the degree that these processes have taken place. Nevertheless, even in highly industrialised countries traditional craft occupations continue to exist, supplying handicraft goods for commercial markets. In the source list the machine operator and the handicraft workers are assigned distinct occupational titles, e.g. the *Handicraft weaver* and the *Weaving machine operator*, or the *Handicraft leather worker* and the *Shoemaking machine operator*. For food manufacturing, the word handicraft worker is not applicable. For bakers and butchers, in most countries the occupational titles will refer primarily to retail trade and a different phrasing is used for comparable occupations in manufacturing.

3.4.12 Subsistence farmers, fishers, hunters and gatherers

The evidence of subsistence workers has been an issue of debate. Due to rapid urbanisation worldwide, the number of subsistence workers is likely to decrease further, although an economic crisis may well lead to a temporal increase of this group. ISCO-08 includes a sub-major group, which is

detailed into the *Subsistence crop farmers*, *Subsistence livestock farmers*, *Subsistence mixed crop and livestock farmers*, and *Subsistence fishers, hunters, trappers and gatherers*. The source list includes these four occupations. For the Netherlands these occupations have been translated with the extension ‘hobby’, e.g. the Subsistence livestock farmer is translated to veehouder (hobby), to be distinguished from Livestock farmer (in Dutch *Veehouder*).

3.4.13 My job title is not in your list

Even with thousands of occupational titles in a look-up table, there will be respondents who cannot identify their occupation in the search tree or via autosuggest. This problem can be solved by making the selection of the semantic matching not mandatory. This allows respondents to key in an occupational title, not to select any of the matches and to continue the survey. For these cases, the survey holder has to undertake office coding. As these occupational titles are likely to be rare titles, the survey holder is advised to include a separate page with survey questions about the keyed in title, for example about the required educational level and the number of co-workers in the same occupation in the country, asked in broad classes. In case of very rare occupations it may be considered less necessary to code the occupation. This procedure also allows to detect new and emerging occupations. Depending on the sample size this office coding may be a time- and budget-consuming operation on the side of the survey-holder.

In case the survey question about occupation is mandatory, implying that the respondent cannot continue the survey unless an occupational title is selected, it is advised to add an extra question asking whether respondent could identify his/her own occupational title and asking for a job description. This allows to identify unreliable answers.

3.5 Testing validity and reliability of occupational measurement

Once the extended database is implemented, a program to test the validity and reliability of the occupational measurement should be developed. To measure the validity, the most appropriate approach would be to ask web survey respondents twice about their occupation, first in an open-ended question and then with the semantic matching tool. To measure reliability it may be suitable to ask web survey respondents in a web panel to identify their occupation with the semantic matching tool in two separate waves, thereby controlling for job changes or changes of employer. We will follow Belloni et al (2016) focusing on coding errors in occupational data. The results suggest that the incidence of coding errors in the SHARE survey is high, even when the comparison is made at the level of one-digit occupational codes, highlighting the complexity of occupational coding. For the occupation data in the WageIndicator web survey the job description text will be compared to the self-selected occupation from either the search tree or the autosuggest.

Finally, the semantic matching tool not only challenges the validity and reliability of the measurement. In web surveys it is common to use additional measures of performance, such as the response times and the drop-out rates at this particular question in relation to overall drop-out rates. These measures should also be included in the test program.

4. What do workers do? Measuring the intensity and market value of tasks in jobs

Kea Tijdens and Stefano Visintin

4.1 Introduction

ILO's hierarchical occupational classification ISCO-08 defines a job as a bundle of tasks and duties performed by one person (ILO, 2012; Hunter, 2014). Jobs with the same set of main tasks and duties are aggregated into 433 occupation units at the 4-digit level of the classification. Thus, an occupational title refers to the same work activities. It assumes also that across countries, similar occupations are coded similarly into the classification. With occupations as a core concept, the challenge arises whether occupations indeed have similar meanings across and within countries. Hence, do similar occupational titles refer to the same job content? Unfortunately, an empirical basis for this assumption is lacking. For researchers the tasks in occupations are a black box. In labour force surveys, as well as in many other socio-economic surveys, the classification of respondents' jobs into occupations is almost solely based on job titles, and only in ambiguous cases coders explore the job description.

This section explores an innovative method to measure how frequently jobholders carry out tasks associated with their occupation and how much these tasks are valued in the labour market. Questions such as *do the same occupations reflect the same work activities within and across countries?* are addressed by exploring the descriptive statistics of the measurement of occupation-specific tasks in a web survey in 13 countries. Furthermore we embark on an exercise which final aim is to provide the market value (in euro) of the implementation of those tasks. Note that this paper solely focusses on the measurement of task frequencies in jobs, using a web survey of jobholders. It does not include the measurement of skills needed to perform the tasks, although skills represent the capacity to perform the tasks. Yet, the measurement of tasks may provide further ideas how to use web surveys for the measurement of skills.

Section 4.2 provides a review of the measurement of tasks in occupations in surveys in Europe. Section 4.3 specifies how the tasks have been measured in the web survey used here. Section 4.4 proposes and implements a methodology that estimates the market value of tasks. Section 4.5 drafts some conclusions.

The initial paper for deliverable D21.1.2 included 7 appendices, all of them were very long (see Tijdens & Visintin, 2016). The appendices are not included in this report, but can be downloaded.¹⁹ Appendix 1 shows the list of the 427 ISCO-08 occupations at 4-digits, for which the tasks were measured. Appendix 2 lists all tasks of these occupations. Appendix 3 provides tables with the mean scores on the tasks. Appendix 4 shows the most frequent answer for each task in each country. Appendix 5 collects the data on valid responses, in particular it shows the percentage of valid responses for each task in each country. Appendix 6 presents the results of the task values estimation. Appendix 7 holds a list of country abbreviations.

¹⁹ See <http://www.uva-aias.net/nl/working-papers/aias/2016/what-do-workers-do>

4.2 Review of previous tasks measurements

4.2.1 Introduction

Do similar job titles refer to the same work activities within and across countries? This question can also be phrased differently. Does an Italian carpenter engage in the same activities as a carpenter from Germany, Slovakia or the Netherlands? The practical relevance of this question refers to European policies to increase labour mobility across borders. The EURES job portal is an effort of the European Public Employment Services to encourage job seekers to find vacancies across borders.²⁰ Currently ESCO, which is an abbreviation for the European Skills, Competences and Occupations taxonomy, is developed, aiming to create a multilingual framework of occupations, skills, competences and qualifications and to support EURES in the aim to find jobs for job seekers.²¹ The well-known O*NET® occupational information system in the United States of America stands as an example for ESCO. O*NET has a long tradition of empirical investigations of the content of occupations.²² Across European countries, hardly cross-national studies have been undertaken to explore if occupational titles have the same meaning beyond semantic similarities and thus if they include the same work activities.

The scientific relevance of the above mentioned question refers to the growing interest in occupations as a core concept in a range of academic disciplines. Occupations have been explored for almost a century in I/O psychology (Morgeson & Dierdorff, 2011), and for half a century in the sociology of occupations (*e.g.* Larson, 1977). In labour economics, the studies on gender segregation by occupation and equal pay exists for several decades (*e.g.* Reskin, 1984).

Beyond the scientific relevance of tasks stands their practical importance. Jobs are essentially composed by different working activities that produce output, namely tasks. Accordingly, the added value of a job can be decomposed in the value added by the implementation of each single task within it. Therefore, the price at which the implementation of each task is paid represents a key information in the process of wage setting.

4.2.2 Occupations are not similar, findings from the Eurooccupations project

One of the first European attempts to measure the job content of occupations on a large scale was taken in the EurOccupations project, which ran from 2006-2009.²³ Its research objective was dealing with the (broad) question: ‘Are occupations similar regarding work activities?’ (see Tijdens, De Ruijter, De Ruijter, 2011; 2012; 2014). The project established research teams in eight countries and aimed to, first, build a database containing almost 1,500 of the most frequent 5-digit ISCO-08 occupations for the eight countries;²⁴ second, to test the similarity of the job content across the eight countries for 160 occupations selected from the database. The selection was based on variation in skill level, in gender composition, in number of jobholders, and coverage of all industries.

Using desk research, the project partners drafted and tested 10 task descriptions for the 160 occupations, thereby building on the work of the O*NET® and its approach of analysing work activities by means of job-specific descriptions.²⁵ A multilingual web survey was designed and in 2007 and 2008 the partners recruited experts through their networks and invited them to complete the survey for the occupations they were knowledgeable about. These experts had to rate the frequency of each

20 See <https://ec.europa.eu/eures/public/homepage>

21 See <https://ec.europa.eu/esco/portal/home#modal-one>

22 See <https://www.onetonline.org/>

23 EurOccupations aimed at developing a detailed 8-country occupations database for comparative socio-economic research in the European Union. Funded by EU-FP6 (no 028987, 2006-09) with BEL, DEU, ESP, FRA, GBR, ITA, NLD, POL, co-ordinated by K.G. Tijdens <http://www.wageindicator.org/main/Wageindicatorfoundation/projects/euroccp>

24 The WageIndicator Foundation has used this database for its continuous, worldwide web survey, but added more occupations and more languages.

25 See <http://www.onetonline.org/>

task of the occupation at stake on a 5 point rating scale, ranging from never to daily. In total 2,468 experts completed 2,950 questionnaires. For a number of occupations the teams could however not find a sufficient number of experts. Then it was decided to recruit jobholders via the Internet, using teasers calling for survey respondents working in a specific occupation. The teasers were posted on the frequently visited national WageIndicator websites on work and wages, resulting in another 1,661 ratings.²⁶ Even with over 4,100 ratings, the EurOccupations study encountered quite a number of occupations with none or insufficient ratings, and when broken down by country, the problem grew worse.

Using interrater agreement statistics (rWG) a lack of agreement or no agreement at all was shown for 51% of the 160 occupations, a weak or moderate agreement was so for 38%, whereas for only 12% of the occupation displayed a strong agreement (Tijdens, De Ruijter and De Ruijter 2014). Across all occupations, in Spain agreement was 80%, in Germany 58%, in the Netherlands 43%, and in Poland 48%. The data revealed that jobholder ratings did not differ from expert ratings. The overall conclusion from the EurOccupations project was that although assumed that occupations are similar across countries, to a large extent they were not. Hence, the main conclusion was that the within-occupation similarity of tasks was rather an idea than a fact.

4.2.3 How to explain the findings?

This raised the question how to explain the unexpected findings? Are occupations diverse across European countries, and does it therefore make no sense to aim for labour mobility on occupational basis? Are the methods and data sources critical for the results, and could a larger sample size per occupation or a larger number than the 160 occupations improve the measurements? If so and if stuck to expert ratings, how to cope with the large resources needed for recruiting more experts? Is the aggregation level of the occupations appropriate to distinguish between different jobs and to group jobholders performing similar activities? Recalling that the EurOccupations study tested the similarity of occupations at a 5-digit level, would a testing of 4-digit occupations change the results? One conclusion from the EurOccupations study stood firmly: surveying occupation-specific task frequencies by means of a web survey was a proper way to test task similarity within occupations, for the technical features as well as for its cost-effectiveness in relation to the volume of respondents to be reached.

In 2013 two projects allowed for a follow-up of the EurOccupations project, notably the InGRID infrastructure and the EDUWORKS project. The follow-up study aimed to collect task frequency information for a larger number of occupations, for 4-digit occupations, for a greater number of countries and specifically from a much larger number of respondents. The EurOccupations project showed that the method to invite experts to rate task frequencies was costly in terms of human resources and that the method to invite jobholders was far less so. The project also showed that a web survey was a proper method to ask jobholders about their tasks. Hence the follow-up study needed a large-scale, multi-country web survey addressing jobholders. For several reasons the multi-country, multilingual, continuous WageIndicator web survey was particularly suited. The survey's advanced technologies allowed for a routing from respondent's self-selected occupation to the related tasks list. Finally, the follow-up study was feasible because of the expertise of the first author as the scientific coordinator of this web survey.

A recent development in the economic academic discourse focusses on the task-based approach analysing the evolution of salaries (their polarisation) and the role played by technological change with this respect (*e.g.* Autor *et al.*, 2003), offshorability of jobs intended as the possibility of performing specific tasks abroad (Grossman & Rossi-Hansberg, 2008) or the transferability of skills across occupations (Gathmann & Schonberg, 2010). This approach mostly classifies occupations according

²⁶ See www.wageindicator.org

to a measure of routine task intensity, aiming to investigate the impact of technology on routine and non-routine tasks. This approach differs from that of EurOccupations, because the latter primarily aims for an understanding of the division of labour within occupations.

4.3 Collecting data to compare job content

4.3.1 Task data collected via the WageIndicator web survey

The WageIndicator web survey is posted continuously at national WageIndicator websites (www.wageindicator.org). The first WageIndicator website started in the Netherlands in 2001, and WageIndicator is operational today in 85 countries, receiving millions of visitors (25 million in 2014). Web traffic is high due to search engine optimisation, web-marketing, media attention, word-of-mouth advertising, and social media activities. The websites provide job-related content, labour law and minimum wage information, VIP wages, and a free salary check providing users salary references on the basis of personal characteristics such as occupation, country and experience. Salary estimations are based on the web survey data. The websites are consulted by employees, self-employed, students, job seekers, and individuals with a job on the side to find information about wages or for their annual performance talks, job mobility decisions, occupational choices and alike. In return for free information web visitors are invited to complete a questionnaire with a lottery prize incentive. Between 1% and 5% of all visitors completes the survey. Approximately 70,000 questionnaires are filled each year.²⁷ The multilingual questionnaire is comparable across countries and is held in the national languages. It is composed by questions about a wide range of work and wage related subjects, including socio-demographics (Tijdens *et al.*, 2010). In 2001, the survey started in the Netherlands, with other countries gradually joining from 2005 onwards.

Task descriptions are core to the task frequency measurement. The EurOccupations project team drafted task lists for 160 occupations, using desk research. In the follow-up study, an existing tasks list could be used. For its ISCO update, ILO drafted descriptions of tasks for all 433 occupational units at 4-digit ISCO-08 (ILO, 2012; Hunter, 2014). For the follow-up study task lists for 427 of the 433 units have been prepared (see Appendix 1 in Tijdens & Visintin, 2016 for the list of occupations).²⁸ For six so-called ‘not-elsewhere-classified occupations’ no task lists have been included. The number of tasks varies per occupation, but the large majority of occupations have seven to ten tasks and for the remaining occupations the number of tasks varies between 4 and 14. In total 3,237 occupation-specific tasks are in use for the 427 occupations, which is on average 7.58 tasks per occupation (see Appendix 2 in Tijdens & Visintin, 2016 for the list of all tasks).²⁹ The WageIndicator team adapted ILO’s task descriptions for the web survey.

The task lists have been translated from English into six other languages: Spanish, Russian, French, Dutch, Portuguese, and Bahasa.³⁰ The tasks could therefore be included in the WageIndicator web survey in 13 countries, namely Argentina, Australia, Belarus, Belgium, Brazil, Indonesia, Kazakhstan, Mexico, Netherlands, Russia, South Africa, Spain and the United Kingdom (see Appendix 7 in Tijdens & Visintin, 2016 for the list of country abbreviations).³¹ These countries have been selected because they represent different regions around the world and have adequate response rates to the

27 Completed questionnaires are those filled in by respondents who have provided information about at least their wage, gender, time of first job, occupation title and level of education. In 2014, there were approximately 240,000 completed and uncompleted questionnaires.

28 See <http://www.uva-aias.net/nl/working-papers/aiaas/2016/what-do-workers-do>

29 See <http://www.uva-aias.net/nl/working-papers/aiaas/2016/what-do-workers-do>

30 The tasks were not translated with the aim to serve the study, but were to be posted in the so-called Jobs&Salary pages of the national WageIndicator websites. Each national website has 433 Jobs&Salary pages with information about the occupation. These pages act as so-called landing pages for a wide range of search terms used in Search Engines. Luckily, the translations could also be used for the web survey.

31 See <http://www.uva-aias.net/nl/working-papers/aiaas/2016/what-do-workers-do>

web survey. The data collection started in November 2013 and was still continuing at the time of writing this report.

The follow-up study aimed to explore the task frequency ratings of jobholders who are asked to rate their own job. In the web survey, respondents are asked to self-select their occupation. For the survey question ‘What is your occupation’, the WageIndicator web survey employs a lookup database that consists of approximately 1,700 occupational titles, all coded according to ISCO-08. The selection of occupation is displayed to the respondent as visible on Figure 4.1. Each ISCO-08 4-digit occupational unit comprises of at least one, but mostly more than one occupational title. To navigate the lookup table, respondents can choose to use a tool for text string matching or a search tree (Tijdens, 2014). Depending on the selected occupation, the survey system identifies the relevant ISCO-08 4-digit occupational unit and shows the associated tasks list. Respondents are asked to tick how frequently they carry out each task on the basis of five answer categories: never, yearly, monthly, weekly and daily. The tasks are displayed to the respondent as visible on Figure 4.2.

Figure 4.1 Screenshot for choice of occupation: selection Chemical Engineer

Source WageIndicator web survey: Paywizard.co.uk

Figure 4.2 Screenshot for the task set of the Chemical Engineer

In your current job, how often do you carry out the following tasks?						
	Never	Yearly	Monthly	Weekly	Daily	Not applicable
Conducting research and advising on, and developing commercial-scale chemical processes to refine crude oil and other liquids or gases, and to produce substances and items such as petroleum derivatives, explosives, food and drink products, medicines, or synthetic materials	<input type="radio"/>					
Specifying chemical production methods, materials and quality standards and ensuring that they conform to specifications	<input type="radio"/>					
Establishing control standards and procedures to ensure safety and efficiency of chemical production operations and safety of workers operating equipment or working in close proximity to on-going chemical reactions	<input type="radio"/>					
Designing chemical plant equipment and devising processes for manufacturing chemicals and products	<input type="radio"/>					
Performing tests throughout stages of production to determine degree of control over variables, including temperature, density, specific gravity, and pressure	<input type="radio"/>					
Developing safety procedures to be employed	<input type="radio"/>					
Preparing estimates of production costs and production progress reports for management	<input type="radio"/>					
Performing laboratory studies of steps in manufacture of new products and testing proposed process in small scale operation such as a pilot plant	<input type="radio"/>					

Source WageIndicator web survey: Paywizard.co.uk

4.3.2 Data and methodology

Between November 2013 and August 2015 33,678 respondents had completed the tasks questions for their respective occupations. Table 4.1 presents the number of observations per country. An observation is here defined as a questionnaire filled in by respondents who have provided valid information about at least three quarters of the tasks listed for their occupation. Appendix 3 in Tijdens and Visintin (2016) provides a table with the number of observations per occupation per country. Observations in which the same frequency (straight-lining) was selected for all the tasks were considered untrust-worthy and therefore excluded.

Table 4.1 Number of valid observations per country between November 2013 and August 2015

Country	Locale	Language	N
Argentina	es_AR	Spanish	1,783
Australia	en_AU	English	116
Belgium	nl_BE/fr_BE	Dutch/French	1,704
Brazil	pt_BR	Portuguese	1,892
Belarus	ru_BY	Russian	3,752
Indonesia	ba_ID	Bahasa	2,147
Kazakhstan	ru_KZ	Russian	3,158
Mexico	es_MX	Spanish	3,079
Netherlands	nl_NL	Dutch	9,729
Russian Federation	ru_RU	Russian	825
South Africa	en_ZA	English	2,935
Spain	es_ES	Spanish	1,516
United Kingdom	en_GB	English	1,042
Total			33,678

Source WageIndicator data November 2013-Augustus 2015

The descriptive statistics of the data-collection are detailed in Appendix 3 through 5 (see Tijdens & Visintin, 2016).³² Appendix 3 presents the total count of valid responses per occupation and country. The Netherlands is the country where most valid observations were collected (9,729) while the most common occupation in the dataset is General office clerck (ISCO code 4110, 1981 observations in total). Other most observations were noticed for the Accounting associate professionals, Administrative and executive secretaries, Shop sales assistants, and Secretaries (general). Hardly any observations were noticed for the Meteorologists, Dispensing opticians, Poultry producers, Riggers and cable splicers, Forestry labourers, and other occupations. Appendix 4 shows the most frequent answer (where 1 = Never; 2 = Yearly; 3 = Monthly; 4 = Weekly; 5 = Daily) for each task in each country. For two thirds of these tasks the frequency varies from 1 to 5 across the 13 countries, pointing to substantial cross-country variation of occupational tasks. Appendix 5 collects the data on valid responses, in particular it shows the percentage of valid responses for each task in each country. It provides information on the drop-out of workers once they are presented the tasks and answered at least to one.

4.4 Estimating the market value of tasks in the Netherlands

Jobs can be decomposed into the units of work activities that produce output, namely the task implemented in their completion and, consequently, the price at which the execution of a single task is paid becomes a fundamental information when setting wages in the labour market.

Here we describe a methodology implemented to estimate the market value of tasks. The market value of a task is here intended as the (hourly) salary paid to perform that specific task. In short, it is estimated as the median of the (gross hourly) salary perceived by workers performing the task intensively (which means on daily or weekly basis).

Given the national scope of most labour markets, it is our belief that this exercise has to be performed at country level. Therefore, we confine the implementation of this approach to the Dutch labour market, but the same methodology can be replicated in all countries in the dataset. Approximately 7000 respondents provided information about both, salary and the intensity by which they

³² See <http://www.uva-aias.net/nl/working-papers/aias/2016/what-do-workers-do>

perform each task corresponding to their occupations in the Dutch section of the WageIndicator survey.

Outlier responses often affect self-reported wage data (see Acemoglu & Autor, 2011, among others). We rely on the following steps to filter noisy information. We first leave out dubious values (gross salaries below 0.5 euro or above 1,000 euro per hour), and subsequently focus on the 1st through 99th percentile of the resulting distribution. Approximately 6,800 wage responses are considered in this exercise.

We (arbitrary) set a threshold of 5 data points in order to be able to estimate the median salary value of a specific task. According to this rule of thumb, occupations for which we have less than 5 responses are excluded. So are all tasks performed on a daily or weekly basis by less than 5 workers. We ended up considering 231 (out of 412) occupations and 933 (out of 3,236) tasks. For each of these tasks we computed the median gross hourly salary of all those workers who reported performing the task intensively.

Table 4.2 Best and least valued tasks, median and average values in euro

Task	Task code	Median value	Average value
Leading and managing the activities of research and development staff	122,303	35.36	33.82
Consulting with engineering staff to evaluate interface between hardware and software	251,203	33.84	32.50
Representing the organisation at official occasions and board meetings in negotiations at conventions seminars public hearings and forums	112,009	33.68	35.90
Planning and directing daily operations	122,306	33.20	32.85
Directing the selection and installation of ICT resources and the provision of user training	133,003	33.20	29.68
Conducting research and improving or developing concepts instruments theories and operational methods related to chemistry	211,301	32.86	35.59
Directing software programming and development of documentation	251,206	32.71	32.13
Representing the enterprise or organisation in dealings with outside bodies	121,108	32.70	36.42
Planning the overall research and development programme of an enterprise or organisation specifying goals and budgetary requirements	122,302	32.33	31.28
Researching analysing and evaluating requirements for software applications and operating systems	251,201	32.29	31.15
...
Washing cutting measuring and mixing foods for cooking	941,102	5.93	6.72
Cleaning kitchens food preparation areas and service areas	941,201	5.75	9.14
Noting what has been sold and collecting goods needed from the stockroom	933,405	5.09	6.24
Receiving opening unpacking and inspecting for damage merchandise from manufacturer or distributor	933,408	5.09	6.76
Directing customers to location of articles sought	933,407	4.26	5.81
Removing goods with past due use-by dates	933,403	4.12	6.06
Filling shelves with goods ensuring goods with the earliest use-by dates are at the front of shelves	933,402	4.11	4.97
Maintaining shelf order by removing stock belonging in a different location	933,404	4.11	5.72
Obtaining articles for customers from shelf or stockroom	933,406	4.11	5.64
Placing goods neatly in bins and on racks and stacking bulky goods on floors	933,401	3.61	5.86

Source WageIndicator data November 2013-Augustus 2015, selection respondents in the Netherlands

A pull of the results is shown in Table 4.2, where the best and least paid tasks are presented. The full outcome of the exercise is presented in Appendix 6 in Tijdens and Visintin (2016).³³ It can be observed how among the most valued tasks stand those concerning leadership and management of teams and firms (*e.g.* Representing the organisation at official occasions and board meetings in negotiations at conventions seminars public hearings and forums is paid 34 euro per hour, Planning and directing daily operations 33). ICT and software development and maintenance are also well acknowledged in the market (*e.g.* Consulting with engineering staff to evaluate interface between hardware and software is paid 34 euro per hour, Directing the selection and installation of ICT resources and the provision of user training 33). Research activities and their management is another group of activities with an elevated market value (*e.g.* by Leading and managing the activities of research and development staff one can earn 35 euro per hour, Conducting research and improving or developing concepts instruments theories and operational methods related to chemistry pays 33). It can also be noticed how tasks belonging simultaneously to more than one of the groups mentioned are amongst the highest valued ones.

On the other end of the table the tasks are reported for which a low market value were estimated. All activities performed by shelf fillers are at the bottom of this ranking (*e.g.* *Obtaining articles for customers from shelf or stockroom* receives 4 euro per hour). Low level food service and catering activities are also paid quite poorly (*e.g.* *Washing dishes and cooking utensils and putting them away* makes 7 euro per hour). Routinary administrative tasks form a more surprisingly (to a certain extent) group of poorly paid tasks (*e.g.* *Performing mail-handling duties in public post offices or privately owned delivery establishments* and *Arranging appointments and collecting payments* pay less than 9 euro per each hour worked).

The added value of this exercise consists in presenting a simple methodology that is able to deal with one of the most relevant questions in labour market negotiation: what is the market value of the capability of executing a specific unit of work activity. It presents some clear limitations, the most relevant being the bias produced by the data availability. Less than 30% of the tasks identified are included in the exercise. However it is our belief that as the volume of data collected grows, this limitation will lose relevance. The estimation of the market value of the hour execution of specific work activities is however significant information to labour market stakeholders, *e.g.* workers, employers and employment services providers.

4.5 Conclusions

This Section challenges the empirical testing of the assumption underlying the ISCO occupational classification that jobs with the same set of main tasks and duties are aggregated into 433 occupation units at the 4-digit level of the classification. Using the task descriptions provided for all ISCO 4-digit occupations, the frequency of task implementation was tested for respondents in the WageIndicator web survey on work and wages. Depending on their occupation the relevant task list was shown.

This section proves that such task measurement is feasible. Moreover, given that the WageIndicator web survey also holds data on wages, the median and average hourly wages (in euro) could be computed for frequently performed tasks. The data challenges future empirical analyses of hypotheses concerning the variation in task frequencies and the related wages within and across countries, across the occupation's skill levels, across firm sizes, across regions and alike.

33 See <http://www.uva-aias.net/nl/working-papers/aias/2016/what-do-workers-do>

5. Validating workshops

5.1 Introduction

As part of InGRID Work Package 3 Expert network programme of workshops, Task 3.2 addressed an Expert network programme on behalf of the ‘Innovative tools and protocols for the working conditions and vulnerability’ pillar. Within Task 3.2 four workshops were scheduled, two of which were organised by the University of Amsterdam/AIAS. The first workshop was held on 10-12 February 2014 and the second on 7-8 November 2016, both in Amsterdam. This section provides brief reports of the two workshops. For the first workshop, see details at the InGRID website <https://inclusivegrowth.be/events/call6-ExpertWorkshop>. For the second workshop, see details at the InGRID website <https://inclusivegrowth.be/events/call41/expert-workshop-call41>.

For both workshops, the calls were made available on the InGRID website, where links to the programme, online application form, financial and practical information for participants were provided. The calls were also listed as news items on the InGRID website and the UVA-AIAS website. Further, the call were added to the (monthly) InGRID newsflash, which was disseminated out to a broad mailing list. The call was also circulated widely by the four partners associated in WP21.

5.2 Validating workshop ‘Developing and testing new tools to measure occupations and their task and skill requirements

The aim of the InGRID expert workshop on 10-12 February 2014 in Amsterdam was twofold. First, it aimed to discuss new approaches of collecting, coding and analysing occupational data, including data collected by web crawlers and web surveys. Second, it wanted to explore possibilities to move towards a joint program of activities for a European-wide harmonised occupational database, including a web-based coding tool.

The first day was dedicated to occupational classifications, the measurement and coding of occupations across countries, in different survey modes and from different sources. This included the design principles of ISCO-08 and the advantages and shortcomings of various occupational categorisations. The CASCOT coding software and the DASISH project for coding job titles from surveys in the UK and abroad were explained. The coding practices of parental occupations in the European Social Survey were detailed, followed by the newly developed method for coding job titles from the Labour Force Survey in the Netherlands. In the last presentation of the day, the requirements for look-up databases were discussed, taking into account the long tail in the occupational distribution.

The second day focused on the challenges related to the web-spidering of job titles in vacancies, the classification of these job titles, and the demands regarding the required look-up databases. Presentations addressed the semantic matching of user-side reported job titles using look-up databases, the parsing and semantic matching of vacancies and cv’s, and the crawling of the Internet for job knowledge. One presentation detailed how task frequencies of 430 4-digit ISCO occupational units in 13 countries were measured in a web survey (see also section 4 in this paper). Another presentation showed a web-based job analysis tool decomposing jobs into larger and smaller tasks. One paper explored how in Hungary graduate occupations and their skill requirements were measured. The supply and demand skills gap was discussed, based on a comparison of educational requirements of vacancies and educational attainment of jobholders. Another paper detailed job matching given

the demographic challenges in the regional labour market in Dalarna County, Sweden. One presentation explored the role of occupations in skills supply and demand forecasts. Finally, the discussion focused on occupations as units of analysis. Presenters discussed occupational segregation in Europe, the socio-economic classifications derived from ISCO-08, and the assessment tools for transversal cognitive skills in individual occupational careers.

The third day was devoted to web-based occupational information systems as well to the discussions about the possibilities for further activities in this field. The relationship between occupations, skills and related training was explored, addressing an ontology-based competency matching between vocational education and the workplace. Another presentation was called 'Increasing the comparability of European occupations by utilising multilingual skills taxonomies: the vision of DISCO and ESCO'. One presentation detailed the method of making occupational forecasts and disseminating occupational information in Sweden. The final presentation concerned the web-based Occupational Information System in Italy. During the conference, one of the leading themes in the discussions focused on the possibilities and the technical requirements for a multi-country occupational coding tool. Since the conference ideas have taken shape, as will be detailed in the next section.

The workshop was attended by 49 persons, of which 5 are associated with InGRID partners and four received an InGRID visiting grant. Participants widely expressed favourite opinions about the workshop. See for the full program, all presentations, photos and report the InGRID website <https://inclusivegrowth.be/events/call6-ExpertWorkshop>

5.3 Validating workshop 'Indicators for job quality, industrial relations, occupations, and new skills and tasks'

The aim of improving the quality of jobs was introduced into the European Employment Strategy at the Lisbon summit in 2000, summarised in the widely cited objectives of 'more and better jobs'. These objectives are still prominent in the Europe 2020 agenda. In response to these policy objectives, the development of joint indicators monitoring the progress of the 'better' jobs objective has been actively promoted. In this context, the EU's 'New jobs, new skills' initiative has challenged academic research to identify not only which new jobs are emerging but also which tools can be used to identify new jobs and their related skill requirements. Sources for occupational information stem from Labour Force and Employer surveys, vacancy announcements, job descriptions as well as job evaluation systems. In social sciences research the occupation variable is widely used and a rich source of information, but occupations are problematic to measure precisely and consistently across countries and in different data collection modes. InGRID's Working Conditions and Vulnerability pillar aims, among others, at developing and testing new tools to measure occupations and their skill requirements. Therefore, the workshop 'Indicators for job quality, industrial relations, occupations, and new skills and tasks' explored the challenges related to this task.

This InGRID expert workshop, held on 7-8 November 2016 in Amsterdam, aimed to explore the state of affairs in knowledge on job quality indicators, industrial relations indicators, occupational measurements, and new skills and tasks measurements. It also aimed at expanding an agenda for future research in these fields. The workshop included presentations of the findings of the research and technology activities undertaken as part of the InGRID's working conditions and vulnerability pillar.

The morning of the first day, 7 November, was dedicated to new skills new jobs: measuring occupations and tasks. Three papers were presented and discussed. Kea Tijdens, coordinator of Work Package 21 in InGRID, presented 'Self-identification of occupation in web-surveys: databases and experiences'. Malte Schierholz (IAB and MZES, Germany) presented his research 'Occupation Coding During the Interview'. Stefano Visintin and Stephanie Steinmetz presented 'Measuring tasks in occupations'.

The afternoon of the first day, 7 November, was dedicated to the topic of new skills new jobs. The first papers focussed on methodological issues. Karolien Lenaerts (CEPS) presented 'Prospects for utilisation of non-vacancy web data in labour market analysis'. Miroslav Beblavy/Karolien Lenaerts (CEPS) presented 'Using meta-data to identify new occupations and skills' and Antonio Lima (NESTA) presented 'A skill-based occupational classifier for web-based job ads'. Followed by a discussion. After the break the papers focussed on taxonomy issues. Miroslav Beblavy/Brian Fabo (CEPS) presented 'The demand for general and IT skills in non-IT jobs in the US'. Brian Fabo (CEPS) presented 'The demand for language skills in the Visegrad Four' Annemieke Biesma (Technopolis) presented 'The impact of game-changing technologies in the manufacturing sector', followed by a discussion.

The second day focused on the job quality indicators, and was chaired by Sylvie Hamon-Cholet (CEE). The first presentation concerned 'The Laeken indicators of QoW: lessons to learn' by Greet Vermeylen (Eurofound), and 'It takes more than one measure: Capturing the multi-dimensionality of job quality with job types and multiple job quality outcomes' by Guy Van Gyes, Anina Vercruyssen, and Lise Szeker (all HIVA-KU Leuven-KU Leuven).

Presentation Measuring vulnerability to adverse working conditions: evidence from European countries Nathalie Greenan and Majda Seghir (both CEE), and a presentation Job Quality and Firm Size in Two Different National Institutional Regime by Zinaida Salibekyan (CEE). After the coffee break, a round table about job quality indicators was organised, chaired by Guy van Gyes (HIVA-KU Leuven). A discussion followed with contributions from Francis Green (University College London), Sonja Drobnic (University of Bremen), and Greet Vermeylen (Eurofound).

After the lunch the topic changed to conceptualisation social dialogue/industrial relations: the indicators challenge, and was chaired by Guy van Gyes (HIVA-KU Leuven). Two presentation were given: Key dimensions of industrial relations: a new conceptual framework (Christian Welz, Eurofound), and Dimensions of industrial relations and efficacy of social dialogue (Bernd Brandl, Durham University). The last part of the second day addressed the issue of measuring social dialogue/industrial relations: the indicators challenge, and was chaired by Maarten Keune (AIAS). Two presentations were given: 'Potentials of the ICTWSS database and the global WageIndicator Labour Law Database' (Kea Tijdens, AIAS) and 'Potentials of the European Company Survey' (Guy Van Gyes HIVA-KU Leuven).

The workshop was attended by 44 persons, of which 16 were associated with InGRID partners and two received an InGRID visiting grant. Participants widely expressed favourite opinions about the workshop. See for the full program, all presentations, photos and report the InGRID website <https://inclusivegrowth.be/events/call41/expert-workshop-call41>

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InGRID

Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion

Referring to the EU2020-ambition of Inclusive Growth, the general objectives of InGRID – Inclusive Growth Research Infrastructure Diffusion – are to integrate and to innovate existing, but distributed European social sciences research infrastructures on ‘Poverty and Living Conditions’ and ‘Working Conditions and Vulnerability’ by providing transnational data access, organising mutual knowledge exchange activities and improving methods and tools for comparative research. This integration will provide the related European scientific community with new and better opportunities to fulfil its key role in the development of evidence-based European policies for Inclusive Growth. In this regard specific attention is paid to a better measurement of related state policies, to high-performance statistical quality management, and to dissemination/outreach activities with the broader stakeholder community-of-interest, including European politics, civil society and statistical system.

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More detailed information is available on the website: www.inclusivegrowth.be

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